

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Interventions in the final phase of elimination and prevention of re-establishment

Section

6.2.2 Targeted testing and treatment to reduce transmission of malaria. In *WHO Guidelines for malaria*, 3 June 2022.

Title

Targeted test and treat (TTaT) for reduction of human malaria transmission in high-risk populations: a systematic review

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This report was reviewed by the Guideline Development Group on Malaria Elimination, convened by the World Health Organization Global Malaria Programme to support the development of recommendations included in the *WHO Guidelines for malaria*. It is being made publicly available for transparency purposes and information, in accordance with the *WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition (2014)*.

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Targeted test and treat (TTaT) for reduction of human malaria transmission in high-risk populations: *a systematic review*

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Summary of findings

Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) compared to no TTAT for reducing malaria transmission

Patient or population: reducing malaria transmission

Setting: An area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential

Intervention: targeted testing and treatment (TTAT)

Comparison: no TTAT

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no TTAT	Risk with targeted testing and treatment (TTAT)				
1. Incidence of Malaria Infection (community level) (Incidence) assessed with: (RDT, Microscopy)	666 per 1,000	752 per 1,000 (546 to 1,032)	Rate ratio 1.13 (0.82 to 1.55)	3046 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^{a,b}	Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) likely results in a large increase in 1. Incidence of Malaria Infection (community level).
6. Adverse Events (Group targeted by intervention) (Adverse events) assessed with: active surveillance	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	2030 (1 RCT) ²	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^c	Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) likely results in little to no difference in 6. Adverse Events (Group targeted by intervention) .
6.1. Severe Adverse Events (among group targeted by intervention) (SAE - Death) assessed with: mortality	7 per 1,000	5 per 1,000 (1 to 47)	RR 0.73 (0.08 to 6.95)	8222 (2 RCTs) ^{1,2}	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^{d,e}	Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) likely results in little to no difference in 6.1. Severe Adverse Events (among group targeted by intervention) .
7. 1 Prevalence of Malaria Infection (among group targeted by intervention) (Prevalence - targeted) assessed with: RDT, Microscopy follow-up: mean 12 months	143 per 1,000	102 per 1,000 (66 to 159)	RR 0.71 (0.46 to 1.11)	4382 (1 RCT) ²	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^e	Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) probably results in a reduction in 7. 1 Prevalence of Malaria Infection (among group targeted by intervention).

Summary of findings

Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) compared to no TTAT for reducing malaria transmission

Patient or population: reducing malaria transmission

Setting: An area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential

Intervention: targeted testing and treatment (TTAT)

Comparison: no TTAT

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no TTAT	Risk with targeted testing and treatment (TTAT)				
7.2 Prevalence of Malaria Infection (among group targeted by intervention (Prevalence - targeted) assessed with: RDT, Microscopy follow-up: mean 24 months)	84 per 1,000	129 per 1,000 (75 to 221)	RR 1.53 (0.89 to 2.62)	4140 (1 RCT) ²	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^e	Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) probably increases 7.2 Prevalence of Malaria Infection (among group targeted by intervention .
7.3 Prevalence of Malaria Infection (among group targeted by intervention (Prevalence - targeted) assessed with: RDT, Microscopy follow-up: mean 6 weeks)	255 per 1,000	110 per 1,000 (84 to 140)	RR 0.43 (0.33 to 0.55)	1317 (1 observational study) ³	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^e	Targeted testing and treatment (TTAT) results in a reduction in 7.3 Prevalence of Malaria Infection (among group targeted by intervention .

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: confidence interval; RR: risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.

Moderate certainty: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.

Low certainty: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: the true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.

Very low certainty: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

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Based on PRISMA 2020 item checklist - <https://www.bmj.com/content/372/bmj.n71>

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Introduction

Addressing the Burden of Malaria

There were approximately 229 million cases of malaria, and over 409 000 deaths due to malaria in 2019.¹ Malaria, caused by the *Plasmodium spp.* parasite, continues to cause the greatest burden of malaria mortality in children under-5, who account for 61% of all malaria deaths. The WHO Africa region bears the greatest burden of malaria incidence and mortality with approximately 94% of all malaria cases and deaths occurring in sub-Saharan Africa.¹ In most endemic countries, malaria is a disease that takes advantage of poverty and disproportionately affects those with low access to care or affordability of treatment options.² The bias that exists in affected populations requires increased efforts to target strategies that can effectively decrease the burden of disease and contribute to eventual success in elimination.

There has been notable progress in the fight against malaria. The rapid decline in malaria mortality from 2000 to 2015 was significant; malaria case incidence declined globally by 27% and deaths due to malaria decreased by approximately 50%. By the end of 2019, about 1.5 billion malaria cases and nearly 7.6 million deaths had been averted since the year 2000.¹ However, the stall in progress since 2015 with malaria incidence and mortality being relatively unchanged – declines of less than 2% each year – continues to be cause for concern.¹ Targets for 90% reduction in malaria as goals in the Global Technical Strategy 2016-2030 are off-track and necessitate innovative actions to guide next steps.^{2,3} The current approaches for progress towards malaria control and elimination requires resources for malaria impact are maximized. Countries will need to expand interventions to achieve universal coverage of the core intervention packages, including improved surveillance to better understand their transmission situation and implement the most suitable mix of interventions for their populations needs. For example, in the 11 countries participating in the High Burden High Impact (HBHI) approach, which was implemented to reinvigorate progress in countries accounting for 70% of global malaria burden and deaths, subnational tailoring of interventions and an urban micro-stratification exercise will aid in better targeting interventions and improving efficiencies given the increasing rate of urbanization.¹

Guidance on Malaria Elimination

The WHO recommended core intervention package includes access to vector control (LLINs, indoor residual spraying), diagnostic testing, treatment, and chemoprevention options which make up key facets in a malaria program.³ To further optimize malaria programs within a country, a good surveillance program is also essential; it is necessary to ensure programs are developed based on true malaria burden, thereby facilitating the process for implementing interventions most suitable for that transmission setting and population need. In the past 20 years, there has been significant progress in the number of countries that reported fewer than 10 000 malaria cases; 26 in 2000 to 46 in 2019, and the number of countries with fewer than 100 indigenous cases; 6 in 2000 to 27 in 2019. Between 2015 and 2019, the number of countries with fewer than 10 indigenous cases increased from 20 to 24.¹ With the persistent need for resources, efficiency in targeting malaria programs using the most appropriate and impactful strategies will ensure continued gains towards elimination.

Elimination strategies should a) accelerate the decline in malaria transmission to a level where intensive surveillance is feasible, b) target specific high-risk groups that may not be captured through routine prevention and treatment services, and c) respond to individual cases to interrupt

transmission.^{4,5} The development of guidelines on these malaria elimination strategies would aid countries in their decision-making processes to ensure the most appropriate approach can be implemented given the epidemiological situation, feasibility, resource availability and population need. The Framework for Malaria Elimination, published in 2017, serves as a manual for operationalizing malaria guidelines by offering guidance on tools and strategies to interrupt transmission and to support a country's progress along the elimination continuum.⁵ Within the continuum, different levels of malaria transmission will require different strategies to maintain progression to zero; these include accelerator, targeted and reactive strategies.⁴

Description of the Intervention

Targeted Test and Treat (TTaT) includes parasitologic testing (with or without prior symptom screening) followed by treatment of confirmed cases with a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine, including radical treatment for infections caused by *Plasmodium vivax* (*P. vivax*) and *Plasmodium ovale* (*P. ovale*). The populations targeted by the TTaT intervention includes high-risk individuals defined based on demographic, occupational and/or exposure characteristics, and considered to comprise a large proportion of the parasite reservoir in an area for malaria infection with human *Plasmodium spp.*⁴ For TTaT, identifying these high-risk groups may serve as an indicator for capturing malaria cases that need to be successfully treated both for their own individual benefit as well as to reduce community transmission of malaria.

Why this review is important

Currently, there are no standard WHO malaria elimination guidelines that offer specific recommendations for use of targeted elimination strategies. In 2015, the WHO convened an evidence review group to evaluate recent studies on the role of mass drug administration (MDA), mass screen and treat (MSAT) and focal screen and treat (FSAT) for malaria transmission reduction and elimination.⁶ FSAT, for example, was considered a targeted approach which deployed screening of individuals in a defined geographic area, followed by treatment if positive, with the aim of decreasing the parasite reservoir in the defined region. The key conclusions from the review of evidence for FSAT were that while modest reductions to transmission can be achieved, transmission interruption and elimination would not be achieved. In addition, the operational aspects of implementation for these strategies, such as drugs of choice, coverage, and contextual factors including community engagement were noted for their significance in the success of a control program. Knowledge gaps were also identified in the pool of evidence available on elimination strategies to inform recommendations for implementation.^{6,7}

As a targeted strategy, conceptually, once transmission has declined to the point that it can be considered focal and high-risk populations are identifiable, TTaT may be efficacious in reducing transmission even further by targeting a group that represents a large proportion of the infectious reservoir. This systematic review served to collate the current evidence to further understand how populations at high risk, and the surrounding populations, could benefit from this targeted approach to malaria control and elimination.⁴

Objectives

The main objective of this review was to assess the relative effects (benefits and harms) of TTaT compared to no TTaT in adults and children at increased risk of malaria infection. Specifically, the aims of this review were to:

- Determine the benefits and harms of adults and children at higher risk for malaria infection in areas with ongoing transmission or malariogenic potential, receiving parasitologic testing and treatment with a therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine compared with no intervention, where benefits are defined as reduced malaria transmission at the community and population level.
- Determine which factors might modify the effects of targeted test and treat strategies in high-risk populations.¹
- Identify evidence on contextual factors including values and preferences, health equity, resource use, acceptability, and feasibility.

Table 1 displays the population, intervention, comparator, and outcomes (PICO) of the review question.⁴

Table 1. PICO Descriptors for Targeted Test and Treat Strategies for Malaria	
<i>REVIEW QUESTION: What are the relative effects (benefits and harms) of TTaT compared to no TTaT in adults and children at increased risk of malaria infection?</i>	
Setting	An area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential
Population² (Targeted group)	Adults and children at increased risk of malaria infection. Risk factors include demographic, occupational and exposure characteristics (including recent travel to a higher transmission area).
Intervention	Parasitologic testing and treatment of confirmed cases at approximately the same time
Comparison	No intervention
Outcome (in priority order)	Community level 1. Incidence of malaria infection 2. Prevalence of malaria infection

¹ Potential effect modifiers to be investigated were: Level of transmission; vector control coverage, malaria parasite species (Pf, Pv, Po or Pm) in the area, antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide and hypnozoiticide, whether or not screening for symptoms used before testing, limit of detection and sensitivity of the test

² The population is the group targeted by the intervention. However, the benefits of the intervention are intended to apply to the wider community by reducing transmission of malaria. Therefore, outcomes were included at both the community level and at the level of the individuals targeted by the intervention.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season) 4. Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases 5. Drug resistance <p>Among the group targeted by the intervention:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adverse events³ 2. Prevalence of malaria infection
Timeframe	1-24 months after the start of the intervention

Methods

Eligibility criteria

Setting Characteristics

Studies selected included research that took place in malaria endemic regions with ongoing human transmission, countries with malariogenic potential attempting to prevent re-establishment of indigenous malaria transmission, and those aiming for progress towards elimination. All transmission levels were considered for inclusion; no, low, moderate and high transmission, and any variations in transmission status between and within different countries.

Types of Study Designs

The study designs considered eligible for inclusion to assess the balance of benefits and harms are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Inclusion Criteria for Types of Study Designs	
Type of study design	Additional requirements
Randomized study designs	
Cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs)	At least 2 clusters per arm
Cluster-randomized crossover trials	At least 2 clusters per arm
Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs	At least 4 clusters
Cluster-randomized factorial designs	At least 2 clusters per level
Non-randomized study designs	
Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials	At least 2 clusters per arm
Controlled before and after studies	At least two sites per arm Contemporaneous control group
Interrupted time series (ITS), controlled or not	Intervention occurs at a defined point in time

³ Further stratified to adverse events and severe adverse events, which were defined by death or mortality

	At least 3 data points collected over one year before and 3 data points collected one-year post-intervention
Uncontrolled before and after studies Before and after studies with historical controls	<i>Note: These studies considered to have a critical risk of bias.</i>
Mathematical Modeling studies	
Simulation mathematical studies based on assumptions Mathematical modeling studies grounded in empirical data from specific study sites	Inclusion criteria was the same as for empirical studies
Contextual Factors Studies	
Randomized and nonrandomized studies including observational and qualitative studies	All study types listed above and in addition case-control, cross-sectional surveys, open-ended surveys, interviews, and focus groups among other qualitative or quantitative study designs

Types of Participants

The malaria-affected populations included an age range from childhood to adulthood, where risk could be at the individual and/or population level. The participants specifically targeted were those defined as high-risk based on demographics (age, occupational, or other exposure characteristics) or special populations identified as significant reservoirs of infection in the area. High-risk populations for TTaT included social demographics and occupations such as schoolchildren, agriculture workers, military personnel, miners, and other laborers, as well as groups with other exposure characteristics including forest-goers, peacekeepers, or other vulnerable populations considered relevant in addressing malaria transmission in areas approaching elimination.

Types of Interventions

Background Interventions. Studies in which other malaria and non-malaria co-interventions were balanced across all arms were included. Co-interventions included the use of ITNs, IRS, source reduction activities, environmental management, mass drug campaigns for other neglected tropical diseases, educational campaigns, and mass nutritional supplementation activities. Existing control efforts also may have included background interventions as a part of the standard of care. For this reason, we expected some studies would take place in areas where adequate access to case management could be available, passive surveillance activities with testing and treatment for the population, and active individual-level chemoprevention strategies, such as intermittent preventive treatment in infants and pregnant women or seasonal malaria chemoprevention may have been implemented. Where possible, we documented details on background interventions as relevant for potential impact on the TTaT intervention being tested in the population.

Intervention Arms. For this review the TTaT strategy was defined as parasitologic testing (with or without prior symptom screening) for malaria infection with human *Plasmodium spp.* followed by treatment of confirmed cases with a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine including treatment for liver-stage parasites for infections caused by *P. vivax* and *P. ovale*.⁴ Interventions that were

implemented as a part of other disease strategies, such as integrated community case management, or community health worker strategies, were eligible for inclusion if the TTaT intervention was retained in entirety.

Control Arms. No TTaT intervention

Time of Follow-up. The timeframe for interventions was a balanced 1-24-months follow-up period for intervention and control arms after the start of an intervention trial.

Outcomes

Studies included in this review needed to assess at least one main outcome for the targeted population or community level as listed in the PICO Table 1. The timing of the outcomes included a pre-intervention baseline period of < 12 months prior to the first round of TTaT and a post-intervention period referring to the time period following completion of the last round of the TTaT intervention. The timeframe for interventions had to include a balanced 1-24-months period for intervention and control arms after the start of an intervention trial.

Exclusion Criteria

This review was focused on targeted testing and treatment of malaria, so studies were excluded where the intervention was compounded with other interventions such as reactive strategies, mass drug administration (MDA), targeted drug administration (TDA), or mass test and treat (MTaT). Studies were also excluded if the main objective was to assess or evaluate the efficacy of antimalarials, drug regimens/ dosing, or diagnostic tests. In addition, we did not evaluate the supply chain, resource management, access to care, and quality of care. While these factors all play a significant role in intervention effectiveness, these program characteristics were not individually assessed.

Contextual Factors

For studies retained for contextual factors all study designs including observational and qualitative studies were included. The contextual factors assessed in this review were defined as follows:

Values and preferences – The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention;

Acceptability - extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention;

Health equity – extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, SES status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all;

Resource use – cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit; and,

Feasibility – legal barriers to implementation, interaction with existing health system, need for, and use of the existing health workforce.

Modeling Studies

For studies retained using mathematical modeling, the inclusion criteria remained the same as for empirical studies, and they were further categorized as simulation mathematical studies based on assumptions or studies grounded in empirical data from specific study sites. Mathematical models could have explored the impact of different intervention design considerations including but not limited to coverage rates, frequency of the test and treat strategy, and season of implementation.

Information sources

The studies included in this review were identified using bibliographic databases as well as project and grant databases, conference proceedings, and expert consultation. No language restrictions were used for inclusion, and both published and grey literature (e.g., reports, documents) were used for study identification. The search strategy used pre-defined search terms, relevant subheadings, and keywords related to malaria, antimalarials, screening, diagnosis, and treatment. The timeframe included all available literature to present-day. The following sources were included in the search strategy:

Bibliographic databases: MEDLINE (PubMed), LILACS, EMBASE (Ovid), the Cochrane Library

Other relevant databases: ZETOC, Armed Forces Pesticide Management Board (AFPMB), The Archives of the World Health Organization, US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (clinicaltrials.gov), ISRCTN registry, The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP), and the MESA Track database⁴

Reference Lists: Reference lists of reviews topics that correlate with TtAT, and studies included in the review from the bibliographic database

Conference Proceedings: American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) Annual Meetings, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health Future of malaria research Symposium, Keystone/MESA Symposium, Women in Malaria Conference, Doctors Without Borders (MSF) Scientific Days 2021, Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN) Journal Clubs (TechTalks), 6th Southern Africa Malaria Research Conference

Organizational and Expert Contacts: Contact of malaria organizations and experts to capture grey literature, reports, and additional resources

Search strategy

A preliminary search was conducted to field the state of the science, assess appropriate keywords and phrases, and gather background information on malaria elimination strategies. The scoping search was developed with the consultation of a librarian from the University of Barcelona. The search was conducted in PubMed, with a corresponding search conducted in the Cochrane Library using relevant categories. The final search strategy for the review was developed in collaboration with a systematic review information specialist using the information sources described above and conducted in March 2021. The final keyword strategy is presented in Appendix 1.

Since four systematic reviews on malaria elimination strategies were undertaken with intervention specific search strategies, studies identified in the other searches that could be included in the TTaT review were assessed at the abstract/title review state to determine eligibility.

Data management

To manage records and data throughout the review, the software system Mendeley Reference Manager⁴ and Zotero⁵ were used. Spreadsheets and documents with corresponding article information were stored using G-suite tools. The overall project details for studies included in the reviews are maintained in MESA Track.⁶ Projects currently in progress were collated and stored in MESA Track as a '*Deep Dive*'; this allows ease of access to projects that may generate relevant results on the impact of TTaT in the future. All title/abstract and full-text reviews were conducted in Eppi Review 4-0 and Eppi Reviewer Web.⁷

Selection process

For the study selection process two authors from the systematic review team separately reviewed abstracts and titles from the retrieved articles. All studies identified as potentially eligible based on the title and abstract reviews were retrieved for a full-text review. The full report was then assessed for eligibility by both authors, independently. The final selections for both the abstract/title screening and the full-text screening were made using an eligibility criteria checklist. For any discrepancies or disagreements in inclusion at either stage by the two authors, the remaining systematic review team members assessed the study for inclusion. For studies where there were still concerns or disagreements on inclusion or exclusion, the WHO methodologist and elimination guidelines development team lead were consulted for final determination. A final spreadsheet including the PRISMA diagram, final list of studies included in the full-text review, list of in-progress studies relevant to the review, and list of excluded studies from the full-text review with reasons for exclusion were shared with the GDG, WHO methodologist and malaria elimination team lead for agreement.

The abstract/title screening process and full-text review process were tested in a calibration exercise using the Eppi Reviewer 4.0 and/or Web tools. Each author practiced the abstract/title screening and full-text review independently, followed by the collective development of a written standard operating procedure (SOP) to codify the screening process. The authors then conducted an exercise to compare and calibrate screening outcomes for the abstract/ title and full text review on a subset of articles using the corresponding SOPs in the Eppi Reviewer tool.

⁴ Mendeley Reference Manager is a free reference manager and academic tool for organizing research and collaborating with others. Website: <https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/mendeley>

⁵ Zotero is a project of the Corporation for Digital Scholarship, a nonprofit organization dedicated to the development of software and services for researchers and cultural heritage institutions, and is developed by a global community. Website: www.zotero.org

⁶ MESA Track is a living database which captures research projects and institutions' portfolios in malaria elimination and eradication. The tool was developed and managed by the MESA Alliance, hosted at the Barcelona Institute for Global Health, and funded by a grant from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Website: <https://mesamalaria.org>

⁷ EPPI-Reviewer is an application for literature reviews, including systematic reviews, meta-analyses, 'narrative' reviews and meta-ethnographies. The tool was developed and maintained by the EPPI-Centre at the Social Science Research Unit of the UCL Institute of Education, University of London, UK. Website: <https://www.eppi.ioe.ac.uk>
EPPI Reviewer was last updated on 15 October 2020 (version 4.11.5.1).

After data extraction and categorization of study information, the included articles were assessed for meta-analysis, narrative or contextual contribution to the review by the primary author with confirmation by a second review team member. Appendix 2 includes Figure A which represents the flow diagram for the review methodology and Figure B which represents an adapted PRISMA flow diagram for study selection and meta-analysis to reflect the inclusion of studies for contextual factors and modeling.⁸

Data collection process

Of the selected studies for inclusion in the review, data was extracted from study documents by the primary author. A secondary author completed an abridged data extraction form for verification of key data for each included study. For any information not specified in study documents, the principal investigators for the study were contacted for consultation on missing information. Imputation methods were not used for missing data or data that could not be retrieved; rather, the study was then assessed for narrative summary and analysis for specific outcomes.

Data items

The data extracted from the studies included both descriptive data, study calculations and measurements to assess comparability and eligibility for statistical synthesis and meta-analyses. Data extracted included: study design and characteristics, methodology, intervention implementation, treatment, baseline data including participant demographics, outcome data and any other contextual study information that was informative in assessing confidence as evidence. The review authors developed the data extraction forms to capture the necessary study variables and conducted a practice exercise for the data collection process. Appendix 2. Table A includes a summary of variables used for extraction.

Study risk of bias assessment

The primary author and secondary authors conducted a risk of bias assessment for included studies independently. Depending on study type, risk of bias was assessed using corresponding tools. For cluster randomized controlled trials (cRCT), the Cochrane risk of bias (RoB) RoB2 that addresses the additional criteria described in section 23.1.2 in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions was used.⁹ The assessment was reported as low risk, some concerns, high-risk, or unclear with results displayed as graphs. This RoB assessment was conducted for each main outcome of the included studies.^{4,9} For non-randomized controlled trials and ITS trials, the ROBINS-I tool⁸ recommended by the Cochrane group was used. If any domain reached a critical risk of bias, the assessment was discontinued, as further evaluation would not influence how the certainty of the evidence was assessed.⁴ For uncontrolled before and after studies, a critical overall risk of bias was assigned due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.⁴ These studies were only to be included if there are no other studies available or if there were no other studies for an important subgroup. If included, a sensitivity analysis was planned, if there were sufficient other studies, by conducting the meta-analysis without the studies with critical risk of bias and then conducting the analysis with the critical studies included. For any study that reached a critical risk of bias, a subsidiary descriptive analysis and report or

⁸ ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions (ROBINS-I) is the preferred tool for assessing bias in nonrandomized studies. Information on the tool and accompanying visualization apps are available here: <https://www.riskofbias.info/>

their estimates of effect was generated. A sensitivity analysis was also initiated for these studies if the effect of confounding needed to be described.⁴

The risk of bias assessments were conducted using pre-defined criteria for GRADE as described in the '*Certainty Assessment*' section below. Any disagreements or discrepancies between reviewers were resolved through discussion or by consulting the other systematic review team members. If a consensus could not be reached, the systematic review team consulted with the WHO methodologist.

Effect measures

Synthesis methods

For studies where a statistical synthesis could be conducted, a meta-analysis of effect estimates was used to combine and summarize the results of included studies. For all studies included, the quantitative data recorded included a measure of effect (e.g. risk ratio or rate ratios) with 95% confidence intervals (CI), and an appropriate measure of variance [e.g. coefficient of variance (k), intercorrelation coefficient (ICC), standard deviations (SD)]. Crude data was recorded for each study including the number of participants targeted in the intervention, number of cases, number of adverse events, and the total number of participants assessed for the outcome in each study arm. For prevalence and adverse events outcomes, crude proportions or ratios were recorded in each study arm, as well as the crude and adjusted measures of effect reported [e.g. risk ratio (RR)] in the study. For incidence outcomes, incidence rates, and the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm were recorded, as well as the crude and adjusted incidence rate ratios (IRR). For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding factors or variables with detectable interaction including risk and/or rate ratios.

Unit of analysis

For cRCTs, crude measures of effect were adjusted to account for study design and clustering effect by using the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) and mean cluster size as reported in the study. If the ICC was not available, an appropriate estimate based on the study methodology for power and sample size calculations were used. If an adjusted measure of effect was reported in the study, the adjusted value and standard error for the log risk ratio [SE (log RR)] was recorded in EppiReviewer 4.0 to conduct the meta-analysis.

Data synthesis

Data from randomized and non-randomized studies were assessed for statistical synthesis separately. A random-effects meta-analysis was conducted for a relative effect estimate when appropriate. If there were only two studies available for synthesis, a fixed-effects meta-analysis was used.

Assessment of heterogeneity

To assess heterogeneity the degree of inconsistency (I^2) was used to determine the percentage of total variation across studies not due to chance. The inconsistency across study outcomes effect measures were interpreted according to a scale of low, moderate, high or very high with values of <25%, 26-50%, 50-74% and >75%, respectively.^{10,11} If there was high or very high heterogeneity, or inconsistency in the direction of the effect determined by confidence intervals, then a meta-analysis was

not performed. Rather, a subgroup analysis as described below was done to try to reduce heterogeneity if there were enough studies. If there were two or fewer studies in the meta-analysis and heterogeneity could not be reduced, the study effects were reported separately.

Subgroup Analysis

A subgroup analysis was planned for an apriori list of prioritized potential effect modifiers. The apriori subgroups to be assessed were:

- Level of transmission
- Vector control coverage
- Malaria parasite species (Pf, Pv, Po or Pm) in the area
- Antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide and hypnozoiticide
- Whether or not screening for symptoms used before testing
- Limit of detection and sensitivity of the test

If subgroup stratification decreased the power of the meta-analysis making a statistical synthesis inappropriate, or there were a limited number of studies, the resultant data was summarized based on key findings in a narrative description.

Reporting bias assessment

Reporting biases were accounted for within the approach used for identification of studies and data collection processes for the review. Meta-biases such as selective reporting of bias were in part assessed by the RoB2 assessments conducted at the study and outcome level, and in the data extraction process, which allowed for identification of gaps in reported outcomes across studies. For publication bias, funnel plots were planned if there were at least 10 studies included in the analysis.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of the evidence for each outcome measure was assessed using the GRADE method (Table 3). Randomized studies were initially ranked as high and non-randomized studies were initially ranked as low. The certainty of evidence was downgraded if there was evidence of the following 1) risk of bias, 2) imprecision, 3) inconsistency of evidence, 4) indirectness, or 5) publication bias. Certainty of evidence for nonrandomized studies was upgraded if there was evidence of a 1) large magnitude of effect, 2) dose-response relationship, or 3) where it is likely that residual confounding would increase the magnitude of effect.⁴

Table 3. GRADE Criteria	
Certainty	Interpretation
Very Low	The authors believe that the true effect is likely to be markedly different from the estimated effect
Low	The authors believe that the true effect might be markedly different from the estimated effect
Moderate	The authors believe that the true effect is probably close to the estimated effect
High	The authors have a lot of confidence that the true effect is similar to the estimated effect

Thresholds for determining public health value of interventions were determined as listed in Table 4. These thresholds serve to ensure consistency in judgements for precision and size of the absolute effect measures for intervention impact.¹²

Table 4. Categorization of effect sizes			
Species and transmission level	Effect size	Absolute difference in prevalence	Absolute difference in annual incidence
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> – Very low to low	Little to no	0 to 0.03% (0-0.3 per 1000)	0 to 3 per 1000 person-year
	Moderate (public health value threshold)	0.04% to 0.1% (0.4 to 1 per 1000)	4 to 10 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>0.1% (>1 per 1000)	> 10 per 1000 person-year
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> – Moderate to high	Little to no	0 to 10% (0 to 100 per 1000)	0 to 250 per 1000 person-year
	Moderate (public health value threshold)	10 to 20% (100 to 200 per 1000)	250 to 333 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>20% (>200 per 1000)	>333 per 1000 person-year
<i>Plasmodium vivax</i>	Little to no	0 to 5% (0 to 50 per 1000)	0 to 125 per 1000 person-year
	Moderate (public health value threshold)	5% to 10% (50 to 100 per 1000)	125 to 250 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>10% (>100)	>250 per 1000 person-year

The summary of findings statements considered for both the size of the effect and the certainty of evidence assessments are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Summary of findings statements criteria				
Effect size	Certainty			
	High	Moderate	Low	Very low
Large	TTaT results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	TTaT likely/probably results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	TTaT may result in a large reduction/increase in outcome	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of TTaT on outcome
Moderate	TTaT results in a reduction/increase in outcome	TTaT likely/probably results in a reduction/increase to the outcome	TTaT may result in a reduction of the outcome	
Little to no	TTaT results in little to no difference in outcome	TTaT likely/probably results in little to no difference in outcome	TTaT may result in little to no difference in outcome	

TTaT: Targeted Test and Treat

For contextual factors assessed in the review, the ‘Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research’ (GRADE-CERQual) approach was planned. The GRADE-CERQual approach provides a certainty or confidence of a qualitative syntheses of studies using the following four components: 1) the methodological limitations, 2) coherence, 3) the adequacy of data supporting a review finding, and 4) the relevance of data from primary studies.¹³ Due to limited studies retained across some contextual factors, descriptive interpretations by Lewin et.al were instead used in narrative summaries.¹⁴

Results

Study selection

The search strategy yielded 1051 records; 929 from databases, 65 from registers, and 57 identified from other methods. Of these, 288 duplicates were removed before screening. A total of 763 records were reviewed for inclusion and 702 were excluded at the title abstract screening stage. Of the remaining 65 records eligible for full-text screening, 25 were not retrieved because they were conference proceedings, abstracts, or trial registrations. A total of 15 reports underwent full-text review for eligibility, 24 reports were assessed for inclusion as contextual factors, and 1 report was assessed for modeling. After full-text screening, 3 studies were included in the review for outcomes, 9 reports were included for contextual factors, and 1 study was included for modeling. There were 4 additional studies that met the inclusion criteria; however, they were excluded as in-progress studies for which no final results or data have been published yet. The detailed Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)¹⁵ Flow Diagram is presented in Appendix 3.

Study characteristics

Characteristics of included studies are provided in Table 6, with more detailed descriptions described below.

Table 6. Characteristics of included studies					
Study	Location	Year(s)	Study design	Intervention	Outcomes reported
Baiden et. al (2016) ¹⁶	Forest-savannah transition zone, Ghana	2009-2012	cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: children < 24 months • Intervention: RDT-based Test & Treatment • Comparator: standard of care/ clinical judgement • Drug: ACTs • Time/Rounds: 2 years from first febrile episode 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence of malaria infection at the community level (24 months follow-up period) • SAEs (24 months follow-up period)
Halliday et. al (2014) ¹⁷	Southern Coast, Kenya	2010-2012	Factorial cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: school children 5-20 years old • Intervention: Screening & Treatment • Comparator: no intervention • Drug: artemether-lumefantrine (AL) • Time/Rounds: 5 rounds - 2 rounds post 3 months, and 2 rounds post 6 months 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (12 months post-intervention) • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (24 months post-intervention) • AEs (24-48 hours post-treatment to 28 days) • SAEs (for 24 months follow-up)

Cohee et. al (2021) ¹⁸	Southern, Malawi	2015	cBAF/ Cohort	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target population: school children 5 - 15 years old • Intervention: Screening & Treatment • Comparator: no intervention • Drug: artemether-lumefantrine (AL) • Rounds: 3 rounds at 1, 2 and 6 weeks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of infection among those targeted (6 weeks post-intervention)
ACTs: Artemisinin-based combination treatments; AEs: adverse events; AL: artemether-lumefantrine; cBAF: controlled before and after; cRCT: cluster randomized controlled trial SAEs: serious adverse events					

Included studies

Three studies were eligible for inclusion in the review: one factorial cRCT in Kenya by Halliday et. al.(2014)¹⁷, one cRCT in Ghana by Baiden et.al (2016)¹⁶, and one controlled before and after cohort study in schoolchildren in Malawi by Cohee et.al. (2021)¹⁸. A total of nine studies were included for contextual factors. Linked to the included cRCT by Baiden et.al. (2016) were 2 studies by Tawiah et.al (2016)¹⁹, and Baiden et.al. (2012)²⁰ that assessed resource use and acceptability, respectively. There were four studies linked to the factorial cRCT in Kenya. Okello and colleagues reported on values and preferences, acceptability, and feasibility in two publications,^{21,22} and Drake et.al. (2011)²³ reported on resource use. Resource use was also assessed in a cost-effectiveness study in Uganda by Batwala et.al. (2011).²⁴ Values and preferences were reported in one study by Yan et. al. (2020)²⁵ in gold miners in Guyana. A study by Mphwatiwa et.al. (2017)²⁶ also linked to Halliday et. al. (2014) in southern Malawi reported on acceptability. Finally, in a qualitative evaluation, Taffon et.al. (2018)²⁷ presented results from three rural Cambodian villages also on acceptability of the intervention. One modeling study was included which simulated the impact of community-based screening and treatment of symptomatic and asymptomatic individuals on parasite prevalence and incidence of malaria infection in children under 5 years of age.²⁸

Interventions

Halliday and colleagues conducted a factorial cRCT in 5,233 schoolchildren in 101 schools in the Kwale and Msambweni districts on the southern coast of Kenya in 2010-2012. The trial aimed to determine the effects of intermittent screening and treatment for malaria on health, sustained attention, and education in low to moderate malaria transmission settings, as well as the impact of a literacy intervention on education.¹⁷ Results from a baseline cross-sectional survey in 2400 randomly selected children who were enrolled in the 51 intervention schools from the cRCT revealed heterogeneity in the prevalence of *P. falciparum* infection by school with some preliminary evidence of strong associations between *P. falciparum* and anaemia.²⁹ During the intermittent screening and treatment, children were screened once per school term for malaria parasitemia using an RDT, and children (with or without malaria symptoms) found to be RDT-positive were treated with a six dose regimen of artemether (20 mg)-lumefantrine (120 mg) (AL) over three days. Five rounds of screening and treatment were implemented; the first baseline assessment in March 2010, the second round in July 2010, the third in September 2010, the fourth in March 2011, and the final round in October 2011.¹⁷

In a cRCT, Baiden and colleagues hypothesized that the effects of a test-based malaria control strategy would increase incidence of malaria and concurrently anemia, while decreasing use of ACTs

based on the increased accuracy of treatment when compared to malaria diagnosis using clinical judgement. The study, conducted in six districts that lay within the forest-savannah transition zone of perennially high malaria transmission in Ghana, was implemented between February 2009 and July 2012. Incidence of malaria was determined in 3046 children under 2 years of age from 32 health center catchment areas.¹⁶ Children participating in the intervention who reported with fever were tested with a RDT and received artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT) when positive. Field workers visited all children at least once every two months as part of active surveillance to document any other febrile illnesses that may have occurred. Children in comparison groups were assessed for malaria using only clinical management of febrile illness presentation at health centers.¹⁶

In a controlled before and after cohort study, Cohee et.al (2021), also targeted school children as an important reservoir of infection in southern Malawi, concurrent with household-based cross-sectional surveys to evaluate the potential impact of school-based malaria interventions on community transmission. A total of 786 students across four schools, were tested and treated with artemether-lumefantrine (AL), if positive, and subsequently assessed for gametocyte carriage in treated and untreated students by qRT-PCR after one, two, and six weeks.¹⁸ The studies were conducted in two sites with high (>40%) parasite prevalence in school-aged children in Maseya and Makhuwira, and two with lower, seasonal transmission (> two-fold seasonal prevalence difference) in Bvumbwe and Ngowe, in 2015, at the end of the rainy season (April–May) and during the dry season (September–October).¹⁸

Outcomes

Incidence of malaria infection was assessed at the community level by RDT and microscopy by Baiden et.al (2016) during the 24 month follow-up period after the first episode of febrile illness in children enrolled in June 2010 and monitored to June 2012.¹⁶ In the RDT-arm, over 98% of febrile episodes were seen at health centers and tested by RDT, compared with a similar median-time to first febrile episode in the clinical judgement arm.¹⁶

Adverse events were measured in the group targeted by the intervention using active surveillance in Halliday et.al (2014). Active surveillance monitored potential events for 24 hours after each treatment up to 48 hours, followed by passive surveillance in schools for 28 days thereafter.¹⁷ Severe adverse events among the group targeted by the intervention was assessed by mortality during the 24 months of follow-up in the Halliday et.al (2014), and Baiden et.al (2016) studies.^{16,17}

Prevalence of malaria infection among the group targeted by the intervention was measured by Halliday and colleagues at a mean follow-up of 12 and 24 months. Prevalence of *P. falciparum* was compared between study groups using finger-prick blood samples collected during cross-sectional surveys for determination of malaria parasitemia and hemoglobin levels, as well as fever screenings with RDT-testing for children with an axillary temperature $\geq 37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$.¹⁷ Prevalence of malaria infection was also measured in Cohee et.al (2021) at a mean follow-up of 6 weeks and assessed with histidine-rich protein 2-based RDTs, molecular detection for all parasite stages using filter paper dried blood spots, and gametocytes using whole blood in RNA preservative.¹⁸

Contextual Factors

Baiden and colleagues conducted a concurrent study during the cRCT in the Brong Ahafo Region of Ghana to assess the acceptability of RDT-based management of malaria among caregivers of children

enrolled in the trial. The study included a combination of a quantitative survey using a structured questionnaire and qualitative focus group discussions. The survey was conducted from February to June 2010 and collected information on demographics, household characteristics, and included three questions on acceptability for testing and treatment. At the time of the study, RDT-based management of malaria had not been introduced into the health centers and there was little caregiver experience with its implementation.²⁰ Also linked to the Baiden et. al. (2016) cRCT was a cost-effectiveness analysis from a societal perspective that assessed costs for the management of febrile illnesses, including training and management costs, costs to the health sector, and household costs for children suffering fever episodes. The analysis also reviewed the estimated costs (and effects) of introducing RDTs to the health system at the health center level.¹⁹

Drake et. al (2011), linked to the factorial cRCT by Halliday and colleagues,¹⁷ conducted a study that assessed financial considerations in a cost analysis of school-based intermittent screening and treatment to determine how variation in the intervention design, and component prices affects program costs. Economic cost was calculated based on implementation over 5 years and guided by a three-step process taking into account resource identification, resource measurement and resource valuation.²³ Another linked study by Okello et. al (2012),²¹ aimed to investigate the local perceptions and acceptability of intermittent screening and treatment for school children. The study used a conceptual framework on individual, social and cultural factors, as well as structural and systemic factors, including supply chain, human resources, health infrastructure and organizational relationships that influence perceptions of disease and acceptability for control measures. Qualitative methods were used to analyze data from 12 focus group discussions with parents of children enrolled in the study and 17 in-depth interviews with head teachers from the selected schools and members of the district school health coordinating committee.²¹ In a third report linked to the cRCT, Okello et. al (2013)²² did an additional qualitative analysis on the process, experiences, and challenges faced in the implementation of the intervention as well as the approaches used in community engagement, consent/assent, communication with community members during the study.

Taffon et. al. (2018) was a qualitative arm to a mixed-methods pilot study on proactive case detection for high-risk mobile populations and forest-goers using voluntary screening and treatment in the Chey Saen district of Preah Vihear province, Cambodia. The qualitative study arm aimed to assess the understandings, expectations, perceptions and acceptability of proactive case detection and mobilization for participation in voluntary screen and treat activities. Nine focus group discussions were conducted with groups of up to 10 community members, purposively selected based on participation in the voluntary screen and treat intervention; three focus group discussions were held in each of the three villages as well as nine in-depth interviews with village malaria workers, village chiefs, deputy chiefs and assistant chiefs from the three villages.

Batwala et. al (2011) conducted a randomized cost-effectiveness trial in six sub-county level government health centers: three in Bushenyi and three in Iganga districts of Uganda. The trial assessed the cost effectiveness of treating malaria with artemether-lumefantrine based on microscopy, RDT or presumptive diagnosis from the societal perspective based on internal costs (public provider costs) and external costs (patient costs) from March 2010 – February 2011. ²⁴ The cost effectiveness of each approach to testing and treatment was analyzed as the number and proportion of patients correctly diagnosed (true positive + true negative) and treated to determine effectiveness, and the incremental cost per additional case correctly diagnosed and treated (incremental cost effectiveness ratio - ICER).

Mphwatiwa et. al (2017)²⁶ conducted a qualitative study, within the context of the Halliday et. al. (2014) cRCT, assessing the impact of a 'Learner Treatment Kit' intervention which trains educators in the management of basic health problems such as diarrhea, eye infections, minor wounds, and uncomplicated malaria.^{17,30} The intervention was implemented in Chikowi, Zomba district in southern Malawi in 29 schools between November 2013 and April 2015. This qualitative study component assessed acceptability of school-based malaria case management following a year of program implementation. A total of eight focus group discussions were conducted with schoolteachers, parents and guardians, and school children from six primary schools, purposively selected based on intervention usage, school size and location. In-depth interviews were also conducted with key stakeholders purposively selected at community, district and national levels. Interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed using a thematic analysis approach.²⁶

Yan et. al (2020) conducted a qualitative study to understand social, behavioral, and cultural reasons for gold miners' care-seeking behaviors related to malaria testing and treatment in Puruni and Mahdia regions in Guyana. The researchers used a human-centered design and social behavior change framework aimed towards identifying solutions that would encourage gold miners to seek malaria testing and treatment services. The Integrated Behavior Model (IBM) was used to guide focus group discussions and in-depth interviews that could help identify factors that may influence behavior, from October to November 2018 with 109 individuals, 70 miners, 17 other mining camp staff, and 22 key stakeholders in the community.²⁵

Excluded studies

A total of 53 records were excluded from full-text screening. Of records retained for full-text screening, 43 were sought for retrieval from bibliographic databases, 9 abstracts from conference proceedings could not be retrieved, and 8 were excluded for incorrect intervention (n=2), incorrect study focus area (n=2), and protocols or trial registrations (n=4). Studies retained for contextual factors and modeling were excluded due to incorrect study focus area (n= 10), published correction paper (n=1), and articles where a full report could not be retrieved, [e.g., abstract, protocol or other document and ongoing studies, (n= 10)]. Of 22 articles sought for retrieval from other sources, 6 could not be retrieved, 2 were excluded for incorrect intervention, 1 for incorrect comparison, and 1 was a cross-referenced article. Four articles were excluded for contextual factors for study focus area (n=1) and study population (n=3). All full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria are listed with their reasons for exclusion in Appendix 3.

Risk of bias in studies

Detailed explanations for the judgements are provided in Appendix 4.

Cluster Randomized Control Trials

Assessments for risk of bias for outcomes in the two cRCT by Baiden et. al. (2016)¹⁶ and Halliday et. al. (2014),¹⁷ are summarized in Figure 1 for overall risk by domain and as percentages for intention to treat analyses for each domain category.

Domain 1a: Randomization process. All studies were rated as low risk of bias for the randomization process. Baiden et. al (2016) conducted randomization at the health facility level and Halliday et. al. (2014) conducted randomization at the school level.^{16,17} No significant differences in the

characteristics and comparability of children enrolled into the two arms of the study were identified in Baiden et.al. (2016). In Halliday et. al. (2014) the geographical heterogeneity observed in the prevalence of *P. falciparum* infection at baseline was considered a reflection of the complexity of factors that influence vector distribution and density as well as vector–human contact and human infection in the study population.

D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants. Risk of bias for recruitment of participants was rated as low for all outcomes.

D2: Deviations from the intended interventions. There were no notable deviations from the intended interventions for outcomes assessed in both studies. In Baiden et. al. (2016) the fieldworkers stationed in each (intervention and control) health facility helped to ensure compliance with the protocol by reminding attending clinicians about the protocol of the study, as applicable to the particular health center.¹⁶ This was reinforced during 4–6 monthly training sessions held for health workers in both intervention and control facilities. In Halliday et. al (2014), 99.1% of RDT-positive results led to treatment across the five screening rounds and 92.6% of these were recorded as receiving the fully supervised six-dose treatment regime. This was used as a proxy for compliance with the intended intervention.¹⁷

D3: Missing outcome data. For all outcomes except adverse events reported in Halliday et. al. 2014, missing outcome data was rated as low risk of bias. In Halliday et. al (2014), adverse events reporting had some concerns due to lack of reporting in the control arm of the trial.¹⁷

D4: Measurement of the outcome. For the incidence of infection outcome reported by Baiden et. al. (2016) and severe adverse events, risk of bias was rated as low. Similarly, for all outcomes reported in Halliday et. al. (2014), risk of bias was rated as low. Both studies followed prespecified and approved analyses plans for measurement of outcomes.^{16,17}

D5: Selection of the reported result. Risk of bias for selection of the reported result was rated as low for all outcomes for Halliday et.al. (2014), as reported primary and secondary outcomes were the same as planned in the trial protocols and registration. However, for Baiden et. al. (2016), selection of reported result was ranked as high risk of bias because although the reported outcome was consistent with the trial registration to assess incidence of malaria, they reported additional outcomes including episodes of malaria which accounted for repeat illnesses, but did not assess number of children in intervention and control arms that had malaria overall. Incidence was instead categorized by all episodes, episodes after first fever and repeat malaria. Crude prevalence or number of clinical cases was not reported. In addition, the researchers conducted a multi-level Poisson regression analysis to calculate incidence and incidence rate ratios for comparison in study arms, but did not perform a generalized model accounting for potential demographics and confounders to assess risk of malaria infection in study arms.

Figure 1. Risk of Bias Assessment for Outcomes in cRCTs by Domain

Controlled before and after Studies

Figure 2 summarizes the risk of bias assessment for the controlled before and after cohort study by Cohee et. al. (2021).¹⁸

D1: Bias due to confounding. Bias due to confounding was rated as low because key variables that could have a confounding effect were assessed in bivariate and multivariable models between participants at baseline. In addition, potential confounders were then accounted for in final statistical analyses and/or stratified by confounding factors (e.g., seasonality, age).

D2: Bias due to selection of participants into the study. Bias due to selection of participants was rated as low because study sites were selected from 30 previously studied sites in southern Malawi, and fifteen students per grade-level (grades 1–8) were sampled using a random number generator.

D3: Bias in classification of interventions. Classification of interventions was rated as a low risk of bias because intervention groups were clearly defined and recorded at the start of the intervention.

D4: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions. There was no evidence of deviations from intended intervention, so risk of bias was rated as low.

D5: Bias due to missing data. Bias due to missing data was rated as low because there was outcome data available for majority of participants and results remained robust. Final included

participants at follow up was 616 (78%); rainy season 311 (77%) and dry season 305 (80%) which was just under the power sample size estimates of 320 (10 students/grade/school in each season), to have 80% power and detect a 40% decrease in the prevalence of infection after the screen-and-treat intervention.

D6: Bias in measurement of outcomes. Measurement of outcomes was rated as low risk of bias because there was no evidence of influence by knowledge of intervention received on methods and analysis and no evidence of methodological errors on outcome assessments.

D7: Bias in selection of reported result. Risk of bias for selection of the reported result was moderate because there were multiple measurements and analyses used within the outcome domain. Contribution to transmission was evaluated four ways: (1) gametocyte prevalence defined as the proportion of participants with any gametocytes; (2) gametocyte density; (3) total gametocyte burden calculated as the sum of participant gametocyte densities; and (4) prevalence of infections with ≥ 10 gametocytes/microliter (μl), and there were only two subgroups used for rainy and dry seasonal cohorts. The outcome measurements and analyses were clearly defined and consistent; and there was no indication of selection of the reported analysis from among multiple analyses or selection of the cohort or subgroups for analysis and reporting on the basis of the results.

Figure 2. Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Interventions (ROBINS-I) by Domain for Included Study Outcomes

Results of studies by outcome

Incidence of malaria infection at the community level

Baiden et. al. (2016) reported on the incidence of malaria in children after the first episode of febrile illness. In the RDT-based intervention arm there were 914 episodes [IR = 0.64 (0.49,0.82)] and 1011 episodes in the clinical judgement control arm, [IR= 0.76 (0.63,0.93)] The crude incidence rate ratio (IRR) was 1.12 with a 95% confidence interval of 0.81 to 1.54, and a p-value of 0.50. The adjusted IRR = 1.13 (0.82,1.55) with a p-value of 0.47. The incidence of malaria infection for all episodes was also reported and not statistically significant [Intervention: 0.99 per child per year (95% CI 0.78, 1.27); Control: 1.05 per child per year (95% CI 0.87, 1.29); IRR = 1.09 (0.81-1.48)].¹⁶

Adverse Events and Severe Adverse Events in the group targeted by intervention

Adverse events were reported by Halliday et.al (2014) using a combination of active and passive surveillance in schools up to 28 days post intervention. Active surveillance detected 4.5% (92/2,030) of children reporting one or more adverse effects within 2 days of receiving treatment, including headache (n = 68; 3.3%), stomachache (n = 38; 1.9%), dizziness (n = 17; 0.8%), vomiting (n = 7; 0.3%), and pruritis (n = 10; 0.5%).

Severe adverse events were categorized for this review as mortality in study participants. In Halliday et. al. (2014), 11 children died: five in the intervention group and six in the control group during the 24 months follow-up period. The causes of death included yellow fever, heart defect, leukemia, drowning, trauma, pneumonia, and pediatric HIV. None of these deaths in the intervention group occurred within 30 days of the screening and treatment intervention so were not attributed to study participation.¹⁷ Baiden et. al. (2016) also documented deaths during the 24 months of the study. There were 21 (1.4%) deaths in the clinical judgement control arm compared with 15 (1.0%) deaths in the RDT-test based intervention arm. The difference was not considered statistically significant ($p = 0.31$). The statistical synthesis for severe adverse events in the two studies yielded a proportion of 0.5% in the intervention group compared with 0.7% in the control group. The relative effect was RR (95% CI) = 0.73 (0.08, 6.95).

Figure 3. Relative Effect of TTaT Compared to No TTaT Intervention on Severe Adverse Events

TTaT: Targeted Test and Treat

SAEs: Severe Adverse Events

Prevalence of malaria in the group targeted by intervention

Halliday et. al. (2014) reported the prevalence of malaria in the group targeted by the intervention at 12 and 24 months. The adjusted risk ratios (aRR) accounted for school-level clustering, demographics including age, and sex, school-mean exam score and literacy to account for the stratification approach used for concurrent educational intervention. The aRR however did not account for *P. falciparum* infection at baseline. Prevalence at 12 months was 14.3% in the control arm and 10.7% in the intervention arm. The aRR (95% CI) = 0.71 (0.46, 1.11) with p-value = 0.131. The prevalence at 24 months was 8.5% in the control arm and 11.8% in the intervention arm with an aRR (CI) = 1.53 (0.89, 2.62) and p-value = 0.124.

Cohee et. al. (2021) reported on gametocyte prevalence in rainy season [Baseline: 31.1% (27.6, 34.5), 6 weeks post- intervention: 12.8% (9.5, 16.1)], and dry season cohorts [Baseline: 25.7% (20.9, 30.4), 6 weeks post-intervention: 8.8% (5.4, 12.2)]. The prevalence of gametocyte-containing infections overall among treated students decreased from 52% (95% CI: 45–58%) at baseline to 11% (95% CI: 7–14%) after two weeks, which is a 79% reduction, and gametocyte prevalence remained low after six weeks [10%, 95% CI: 6–14%]. Among untreated students (RDT-negative), the prevalence of gametocyte-containing infections remained unchanged from baseline [9% (95% CI: 5–14%)] to six weeks after the intervention [12% (95% CI: 7–17%)].¹⁸ For the combined rainy and dry season cohorts, the prevalence decreased from 28% at baseline to 11% at 6 weeks post-intervention. The relative effect for crude prevalence of gametocyte containing infections was RR = 0.43 (95%CI: 0.33, 0.55).¹⁸

Certainty of evidence

Incidence of malaria infection at the community level

Based on the results from one study by Baiden et. al., (2016) at 24 months intervention, TTaT likely results in a large increase in incidence of malaria infection at the community level (large effect and moderate certainty of evidence). This aligns with the hypothesis of the authors, although based on the insignificant difference between incidence rates in both study arms and the relative effect, this large increase was not observed in the <5-year-old children in this high-transmission setting.

Adverse Events and Severe Adverse Events

Based on adverse events reported by Halliday et.al. (2014) using active and passive surveillance, TTaT likely results in little to no difference in adverse events in the group targeted by intervention. For severe adverse events, results from two studies by Baiden et. al. (2016) and Halliday et. al. (2014), TTaT likely results in little to no difference in severe adverse events among group targeted by intervention (little effect size and moderate certainty of evidence).

Prevalence of malaria among group targeted by intervention

Evidence from one study by Halliday et. al. (2014) reporting prevalence of malaria among the group targeted by the intervention, indicated that TTaT probably results in a reduction in prevalence of malaria at 12 months, but also that TTaT probably increases prevalence of malaria at 24 months. The study concluded that implementing school-based intermittent screening and treatment with AL in a low to moderate transmission setting had no health benefits. In a nonrandomized study by Cohee et. al.

(2021), TTaT results in a reduction in prevalence of malaria among the group targeted by the intervention at 6 weeks post-intervention (moderate effect, high certainty of evidence).

Results of Studies for Contextual Factors and Modeling

Resource Use

Resource use was assessed based on three studies by Batwala et.al. (2011), Drake et. al. (2011) and Tawiah et. al. (2016).^{19,23,24} Both Batwala et.al. (2011) and Tawiah et. al. (2016) conducted cost effectiveness studies. Tawiah et. al. (2016), linked to the cRCT by Baiden et. al. in Ghana, aimed to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of introducing mRDTs in lower-level public health centers where malaria diagnosis was typically presumptive. Researchers found that implementation of test-based malaria case management led to an increase in appropriately treated children at US\$18.6 per additional appropriately treated child compared to presumptive diagnosis and treatment. From a societal perspective the cost was further reduced to US\$11.0 per appropriately treated child if costs borne by households were included.¹⁹ In Uganda, the study by Batwala et.al. (2017) assessed cost for three malaria diagnostic strategies in remote primary care centers following National policies for use of RDTs to target AL treatment to only parasitemic patients. They found that the use of RDTs increased the cost of diagnosis by US\$ 0.67 (about 108% increase) in comparison with presumptive diagnosis; however, similar to the study by Tawiah et. al. (2016), effectiveness of RDT use, if clinicians adhere to test results, provided improved quality of care and cost-effectiveness for overall malaria case management.²⁴ Use of RDTs was considered the most cost-effective with an ICER of US\$5.0 compared to microscopy at US\$9.61 per case correctly diagnosed and treated. Drake et. al. (2011), linked to the cRCT by Halliday et. al. (2014)¹⁷ concluded that intermittent screening and treatment in schools was a relatively expensive intervention costing US\$ 6.61 per child screened.²³ Main costs incurred were for RDTs and salaries to do supervised treatment administration. Researchers concluded that to make the intervention more cost effective, cheaper RDTs and unsupervised treatments could reduce costs by up to 47%.²³ Overall, TTaT can be considered cost effective for targeting children under 5 years of age when compared to presumptive treatment when using RDTs for diagnosis. However, for school-based implementation, TTaT intervention costs can be substantial and expensive for human resource costs and depending on selected RDT use.

Feasibility

Feasibility was assessed in one study by Okello et. al. (2013) in terms of the ability to address key challenges during the implementation of the intervention.²² The researchers highlighted the importance of adequate consent and community engagement processes in school-based research. In addition, they concluded that teachers are critical in school-based health research so having their support and active involvement is essential for success. For community engagement the process must be dynamic and responsive to community concerns and needs. These social aspects to the implementation process including the community and key stakeholders would contribute to the feasibility of implementing school-based intermittent screening and treatment.²²

Values & Preferences

Values and preferences were reported in two studies by Okello et.al. (2012) and Yan et.al. (2020).^{21,25} Okello et. al. (2012) found that parents, health workers, and educators all perceived

intermittent screening and treatment in schools to contribute to a reduction in clinical disease and considered malaria control important. However, few participants were aware that the principal aim of the intervention was the reduction of asymptomatic parasitemia, rather than the treatment of clinical disease.²¹ Yan et. al. (2020) assessed the value of malaria testing and reasons why miners may not pursue the recommended course of treatment. Researchers found that miners self-medicate so they can resume mining activities as soon as possible and are willing to pay what is required to address their symptoms. Additionally, treatment adherence was more likely if testing was conducted indicating a value and preference for test-based diagnosis and treatment as well as the importance of treating infection. However, due to side effects of treatment and the financial pressures to return to work, most miners stopped treatment as soon as they felt better. It was evident that services were usually sought when in close proximity, and there was a preference for public service treatment over private services where quality and reliability were sometimes a concern.

Health Equity

Health equity was not addressed by any studies retained for contextual factors. However, in all of the included studies in the review demographics included gender stratifications to ensure balance in study arms. Results for baseline surveys all found no significant differences in infection by gender.

Acceptability

Acceptability was assessed based on five studies: Baiden et.al. (2012), Mphwatiwa et. al. (2017), Okello et. al. (2012), Okello et. al. (2013), and Taffon et. al. (2018). Mphwatiwa et. al. (2017) was linked to the cRCT by Halliday et. al., (2014) and found that the use of RDTs and ACTs by teachers is an acceptable way of delivering care for malaria to schoolchildren. Benefits of school-based intermittent screening and treatment included a perception of improved access to malaria treatment for school children; decreased school absenteeism; and that the program supported broader national health and education policies.²⁶ Potential barriers to successful implementation disclosed by study participants included increased teacher workloads, a feeling of inadequate supervision from health workers, lack of incentives and concerns for the sustainability regarding the supply of drugs and commodities.²⁶ In Okello et.al (2012) lack of awareness that intermittent screening and treatment was intended to treat asymptomatic parasitemia, did not appear to impact on the acceptability of the intervention. However, some parents expressed concern that their children were given malaria treatment when they were perceived to be healthy, so encouraged their children not to take their medication and instead used the drugs to treat other sick siblings or throw it away.²¹ The researchers concluded that, while the concept of screening and treatment for malaria is generally acceptable, adherence to treatment given to children with asymptomatic parasitemia may be problematic.²¹ Okello et. al. (2013) also found that the intervention in schools were acceptable to teachers, and the community so long as engagement and concerns were addressed adequately throughout the implementation process.²² In the study by Baiden et. al. (2012) acceptability of RDT-based management of malaria was based on perceptions that confirming malaria diagnosis before giving ACT for treatment would improve likelihood of curative therapy and good prognosis, while management on the basis of clinical judgement was considered speculative and could lead to unfavorable clinical outcomes.²⁰ Amongst caregivers for children under 5 years of age, the RDT- based treatment was indicative of improvements in the quality of care and the health system. In the evaluation by Taffon et. al. (2018) the acceptability of the proactive case detection screening activities was related to the perceived simplicity and reliability of the intervention and the

perceived efficacy of the drug used for treatment, if positive. The forest goers and plantation workers that participated in the focus groups indicated that the intervention was not only acceptable, but also that those who could not participate hoped to have an opportunity to participate in the future. Lack of participation in voluntary screening and treatment was associated with availability, and the need choose between working in the field or staying in the village to get tested.²⁷

Modeling

One study was retained for modeling by Kern et. al. (2011). In addition, the study by Cohee et. al (2021) conducted a model estimate for effects of TtT to community prevalence of malaria infection.¹⁸ Kern et. Al. (2011) conducted a modeling and simulation analysis using a deterministic compartmental model based on the basic parasite model of malaria transmission in human and mosquito populations.^{28,31} The deterministic compartmental model allows subjects to move between different states of susceptibility, infection and recovered (SIR) using estimates for the 'infected state' based on a rate determined by mosquito density (m), the human biting rate (b), the prevalence of infectiousness in the mosquito population (A), and the probability of a subject developing a blood-stage infection. The latter stages for recovery have two states for treated and untreated that progresses through four different levels of the model that expresses the degree of infectivity of the subject to mosquitoes, before entering the fourth stage in which subjects recover and return to the susceptible state.²⁸ Kern et.al. (2011)²⁸ determined through this computer simulations that community screening and treatment targeting vulnerable populations under 5 years of age, had the largest effect when performed in an area with high endemicity (entomological inoculation rate, EIR > 200). However, the rate of infection returned to its normal levels in the subsequent year if the intervention was not repeated. The strongest decrease in malaria incidence in the target population was observed with a total of three campaign rounds conducted in close succession, separated by one month each for three months. When the intervention was implemented three months apart, at months 1, 3 and 6 of the dry season, the effectiveness of the intervention was decreased and the subsequent impact on the next malaria season was also reduced. In areas with low disease burden (EIR < 10) the reduction was sustained for over three years after a single intervention. The simulation results indicated that the intervention could reduce the pool of infectious vectors for malaria transmission by treating asymptomatic carriers of *P. falciparum* in an area with seasonal transmission and moderate malaria incidence, and that by combining it with other interventions, it is possible to reduce malaria transmission.

In the simulation reported by Cohee et.al. (2021) as a part of their cohort study, an estimated effect of the screen-and-treat intervention could result in at least six weeks of reductions in the community prevalence of gametocyte-containing infections (26% in the rainy and 34% in the dry season), if the intervention were extended to all school attendees in the community. The total gametocyte burden (sum of gametocyte densities) in the community would be reduced by 33% in the rainy season and 25% in the dry season. This estimate was based on the cross-sectional surveys that indicated a comparable gametocyte burden in the community in school aged children of 47% despite making up approximately 35% of the population.¹⁸

Discussion

Summary of main results

The certainty of evidence for outcomes estimating the effect of TTaT compared with no TTaT was moderate to high. Incidence of malaria infection was measured by one study, Baiden et. al. (2016). Based on a large effect and moderate certainty of evidence TTaT likely results in a large increase in incidence of malaria infection at the community level when compared to the standard of care using clinical judgement. The large effect on increased incidence is expected to be a reflection of improved diagnosis and treatment of febrile patients rather than an indication of increased risk of infection. Adverse events and severe adverse events both had a moderate certainty of evidence based on two studies by Baiden et. al. (2016) and Halliday et. al. (2014). TTaT likely results in little to no difference in adverse events and severe adverse events among the group targeted by the intervention. Halliday et. al. (2014) monitored adverse events using active surveillance for 2 days and passive surveillance in schools for up to 28 days. The most common adverse event detected was headache in 3.3% of children in the intervention arm. Severe adverse events recorded in both Halliday et. al. and Baiden et. al., were considered not significantly different between intervention and control arms, nor were they considered to be associated with the treatment given in the intervention due to the causes of death and timeline respective to the intervention.^{16,17} Evidence for prevalence of malaria infection was assessed based on results from one study by Halliday et. al. (2014) at 12- and 24-months follow-up period post intervention. These two time points revealed inconsistent results, neither of which had a statistically significant relative effect; however, based on the certainty of evidence at 12 months post-intervention TTaT probably results in a reduction in prevalence of malaria, but at 24 months TTaT probably increases prevalence of malaria. This aligns with the modeling simulation by Kern et. al. (2011) which found that the rate of infection would return to normal levels in the subsequent year if the intervention was not repeated in an area with moderate to high endemicity. In the region in Kenya where the Halliday et. al. (2014) was conducted, (EIR) was estimated at 231–269 infective bites per person per year, and in the Kern et. al. (2011) simulation the EIR was >200. Though the modeling simulation used community screening and treatment, they did assess the impact based on a targeted high-risk population of children under 5. Prevalence of malaria infection was also assessed at 6 weeks post-intervention in one nonrandomized study by Cohee et. al. (2021). The study had high certainty of evidence based on an upgrade due to the magnitude of the effect and indicated that TTaT results in a reduction in malaria prevalence among the group targeted by the intervention. In their simulated results using similar timeframes, Cohee et. al. (2021) also estimated the community impact of TTaT would be similar to what was exhibited in the study population. Model estimates based on community data projected a 26% decline in prevalence in the rainy season and 34% in the dry season.

In studies assessing contextual factors, three studies by Batwala et.al. (2011), Drake et. al. (2011) and Tawiah et. al. (2016) indicated that TTaT using RDT-based testing can be considered cost effective for targeting children under 5 years of age when compared to presumptive treatment.^{19,23,24} However, school based TTaT implementation can be costly due to human resource costs and depending on the selected RDT used.²³ Okello et. al. (2013) considered the implementation of school-based intermittent screening and treatment feasible as long as community engagement and key stakeholders were incorporated into the process.²² Okello et.al. (2012) and Yan et.al. (2020) both determined that TTaT was valued as an intervention aimed to decrease malaria incidence and preferred the use of testing for diagnosis prior to treatment.^{21,25} However, in Okello et. al. (2012), it was noted that when targeting

asymptomatic parasitemia, it was often not understood since children without symptoms were perceived healthy, causing parents some reluctance to give children the medication.²¹ Acceptability was assessed based on five studies: Baiden et.al. (2012), Mphwatiwa et. al. (2017), Okello et. al. (2012), Okello et. al. (2013), and Taffon et. al. (2018). All of these studies concluded that TTaT is an acceptable intervention in a variety of settings due to the simplicity of the intervention, perceived indication for improved quality of care, perceived efficacy of test-based diagnosis used to inform treatment and subsequently prognosis. However, when using the intervention to target and treat children with asymptomatic parasitemia, there may be issues with compliance since there is no clinical disease evident to caregivers.

Future iterations of the review should consider asymptomatic parasitemia and gametocyte carriage as main outcomes. While these individuals may not be considered high risk due to disease severity or outcome, they may represent the population that poses a significant contribution to transmission in moderate and low transmission settings and serve as an important reservoir of infection as indicated in the Cohee et. al. (2021) study in southern Malawi in schoolchildren. In addition, submicroscopic parasite carriage is considered common in low-endemic settings and in chronic infections.³² Targeting this population can improve surveillance efforts for understanding the epidemiology of malaria infection within a population and help to estimate the true burden of infection in a community. In addition, given these individuals can still facilitate transmission to mosquitoes, but can often be missed by RDTs, they can be considered significant in perpetuating the transmission cycle, as well as a neglected group for treatment if clinical care is not perceived as needed or sought after due to lack of clinical disease. In Cohee et. al. (2021), 16% percent (unweighted 38/180) of all students with gametocyte-containing infections and 9% (unweighted 4/32) with infections containing ≥ 10 gametocytes/ μl were RDT-negative so were not treated as a part of the school based intermittent screening and treatment intervention. RDTs were less likely to detect gametocyte-containing infections at lower densities.¹⁸ The difficulty is in order to identify asymptomatic infections; a targeted test and treat approach will only work if the targeted high-risk population is also the population, which harbors the major reservoir of asymptomatic infections. Some studies have carried out community-wide mass screen and treat interventions,^{33,34} so were not eligible for inclusion in this review, however an aim in those studies also included targeting a high-risk population such as children under 5, schoolchildren, and asymptomatic carriers, but used a mass screening approach to assess impact to the vulnerable groups similar to the modeling simulation included by Kern et. al. (2011).

Studies using innovative strategies for voluntary test and treat, as in Taffon et. al. (2020) in forest goers and plantation workers in Cambodia, or self-test and treat in gold miners in Guyana by Dounine et. al. (2021) has increasingly aimed to address access to screening and treatment for high-risk populations known to be key reservoirs of infection in their respective regions.^{27,35,36} These populations represent high-risk, but a conventional TTaT intervention is not necessarily as feasible. School based interventions have increased in focus because they target both a high-risk group and, in some settings, an important reservoir for infection.^{17,18,37} However, important to note, is that despite potentially large impacts to both the targeted population and to community transmission, neither study included in this review identified significant long-term effects of the intervention in the study populations.^{18,28,29} In a school based preventative treatment of malaria systematic review which assessed the estimated effect of varied school-based programs, including intermittent preventative treatment, chemoprevention, and intermittent screening and treatment, there was a 72% reduction in the prevalence of *P. falciparum*

infection in the study level meta-analysis and considered effective across all transmission settings. The analyses included 11 studies, and showed strong evidence of heterogeneity across studies, that could not be explained by follow-up time post-intervention among other intervention factors.³⁸ However, short-term impacts at 6 weeks follow-up was evident in Cohee et. al. (2021), whereas Halliday et. al. (2014), found no statistically significant benefit at 12 or 24-months follow-up post intervention. This was perhaps due to differences in the setting for the study; Halliday et. al. (2014) found considerable heterogeneity in transmission in the area and assumed the possibility for rapid reinfection was high.

This systematic review aimed to assess the relative effects of TTaT in high-risk populations based on demographics, occupational and other exposure characteristics, however the PICO question did not account for targeting the important reservoirs of infection, which are key in assessing impact of a targeted strategy. As previously stated, for targeted strategies, conceptually, once transmission has declined to the point that it can be considered focal and high-risk populations are identifiable, TTaT may be efficacious in reducing transmission even further by targeting a group that represents a large proportion of the infectious reservoir. Moreover, an important aspect of elimination strategies includes targeting those specific high-risk groups that may not be captured through routine prevention and treatment services, which may include asymptomatic carriers of infection. Future iterations of this review should ensure consideration for populations proven to host the vast majority of the reservoir of infection in lower transmission settings to determine effectiveness of the intervention.

Other information

Registration and protocol

The review protocol has been registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), registration number: CRD42021232451.

Support

The Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance (MESA) (OPP1159477) is funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

This systematic review was conducted as a part of the guideline development process for the Global Malaria Programme, World Health Organization HQ, Geneva. The WHO Guideline Development Group and WHO methodologist provided expert advice in the formation of the review methodology and evidence to decision process for interpretation and recommendations.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Availability of data, code, and other materials

The review documents including data templates/forms and detailed data extracted from included studies are available by request and primary information on included studies is available in MESA Track. Data analyses and code are not publicly available since they were conducted in a subscription-based software (Eppi-Reviewer).

Acknowledgements

The review authors thank Vittoria Lutje, Information Specialist, for assistance conducting the bibliographic database literature search strategy.

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Appendix 1. Search Strategy

Database: Ovid MEDLINE(R) and Epub Ahead of Print, In-Process, In-Data-Review & Other Non-Indexed Citations, Daily and Versions(R) <1946 to March 30, 2021>

Search Strategy:

- 1 malaria/ (46272)
- 2 exp malaria, falciparum/ or exp malaria, vivax/ (21242)
- 3 malaria ovale.mp. or Plasmodium ovale/ (298)
- 4 plasmodium malariae.mp. (1321)
- 5 Antimalarials/ (26641)
- 6 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 (77179)
- 7 Disease Eradication/ or elimination.tw. (144681)
- 8 (tailored adj2 (intervention* or treatment* or strateg* or administration)).tw. (10066)
- 9 (relapse adj2 prevention).mp. (4142)
- 10 (Presumptive adj2 (treatment or therapy)).tw. (721)
- 11 ((focal adj2 drug administration) or "focal MDA").tw. (33)
- 12 "focal testing and treatment".tw. (2)
- 13 (targeted adj2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration)).tw. (27313)
- 14 (focused adj2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration)).tw. (11099)
- 15 Forests/ or Miners/ or Military Personnel/ (51103)
- 16 ("Forest-goers" or Vulnerable or Worksites or Farm* or plantation* or mining or miner* or laborers or cultivators or military or "armed forces" or "peace-keepers" or agricultural).tw. (508140)
- 17 "high risk population*".tw. or Risk Factors/ (867788)
- 18 "special populations".tw. (2153)
- 19 ("high exposure" or "highly exposed" or "high transmission" or hotspot*).tw. (25219)
- 20 (diagnostic techniques and procedures).mp. (5945)
- 21 Diagnostic Tests, Routine/ (13002)
- 22 Point-of-Care Testing/ or Clinical Laboratory Techniques/ (25458)
- 23 (screening or screened or diagnosed or diagnostics or test*).tw. (4343534)
- 24 "rapid diagnostic test*".mp. or RDT*.tw. (4798)
- 25 "rapid diagnostic test*".mp. or RDT*.tw. (4798)
- 26 "Parasitologic adj test*".mp. or "symptom screening".tw. (427)

- 27 case detection.mp. (2811)
- 28 (PACD or ACD).tw. (5630)
- 29 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 (4370377)
- 30 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 (196928)
- 31 malaria.mp. (96234)
- 32 6 or 31 (104553)
- 33 29 and 30 and 32 (1456)
- 34 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 (1402929)
- 35 33 and 34 (223)
- 36 (malaria test and treat).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms] (10)
- 37 "testing and treating".mp. (162)
- 38 ("Targeted test and treat " or TTaT).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms] (49)
- 39 37 or 38 (211)
- 40 6 and 39 (7)
- 41 35 or 36 or 40 (239)

Database: Embase 1947-Present, updated daily

Search Strategy:

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- 1 malaria/ (85653)
 - 2 exp malaria falciparum/ or exp Plasmodium vivax malaria/ (19974)
 - 3 malaria ovale.mp. or Plasmodium ovale/ (1362)
 - 4 plasmodium malariae.mp. (2655)
 - 5 antimalarial agent/ (27049)
 - 6 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 (116229)
 - 7 Disease Eradication/ or elimination.tw. (195433)
 - 8 (tailored adj2 (intervention* or treatment* or strateg* or administration)).tw. (14012)

- 9 (relapse adj2 prevention).mp. (6349)
- 10 (Presumptive adj2 (treatment or therapy)).tw. (1021)
- 11 ((focal adj2 drug administration) or "focal MDA").tw. (57)
- 12 "focal testing and treatment".tw. (6)
- 13 (targeted adj2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration)).tw. (40070)
- 14 (focused adj2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration)).tw. (14872)
- 15 Forests/ or Miner/ or Military Personnel/ (24834)
- 16 ("Forest-goers" or Vulnerable or Worksites or Farm* or plantation* or mining or miner* or laborers or cultivators or military or "armed forces" or "peace-keepers" or agricultural).tw. (646854)
- 17 "high risk population*".tw. or Risk Factor/ (1128371)
- 18 "special populations".tw. (2849)
- 19 ("high exposure" or "highly exposed" or "high transmission" or hotspot*).tw. (32809)
- 20 (diagnostic techniques and procedures).mp. (1684)
- 21 Diagnostic Test/ (82531)
- 22 point of care testing/ or laboratory technique/ (17386)
- 23 (screening or screened or diagnosed or diagnostics or test*).tw. (6286374)
- 24 "rapid diagnostic test*".mp. or RDT*.tw. (7274)
- 25 malaria rapid test/ (838)
- 26 "Parasitologic adj test*".mp. or "symptom screening".tw. (601)
- 27 case detection.mp. (3722)
- 28 (PACD or ACD).tw. (9127)
- 29 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 (6336580)
- 30 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 (270138)
- 31 malaria.mp. (131088)
- 32 6 or 31 (143569)
- 33 29 and 30 and 32 (2472)
- 34 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 (1788426)
- 35 33 and 34 (474)
- 36 (malaria test and treat).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword, floating subheading word, candidate term word] (21)

37 "testing and treating".mp. (251)

38 ("Targeted test and treat " or TTaT).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword, floating subheading word, candidate term word] (69)

39 37 or 38 (320)

40 6 and 39 (20)

41 35 or 36 or 40 (511)

Biosis previews (Web of science)

TOPIC: (malaria or plasmodium) AND TOPIC: ("targeted test* and treat*")

Indexes=BIOSIS Previews Timespan=All years

Database : LILACS

Search on : (malaria or plasmodium) [Words] and test\$ and treat\$) or (testing and treating) [Words]

References found : 0

Search Name: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

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ID Search Hits

#1	(malaria):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)	6707
#2	vivax	688
#3	MeSH descriptor: [Malaria, Vivax] explode all trees	217
#4	MeSH descriptor: [Malaria] this term only	1700
#5	MeSH descriptor: [Malaria, Falciparum] explode all trees	1480
#6	plasmodium ovale or malaria ovale	63
#7	MeSH descriptor: [Plasmodium malariae] explode all trees	14
#8	#1 or #2 or #3 or #4 or #5 or #6	6709
#9	MeSH descriptor: [Antimalarials] explode all trees	1745
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Disease Eradication] explode all trees	94
#11	(elimination):ti,ab,kw	12206
#12	(tailored near/2 (intervention* or treatment* or strateg* or administration))	3214
#13	(relapse near/2 prevention)	2884
#14	Presumptive near/2 (treatment or therapy)	160
#15	focal near/2 (drug administration) or "focal MDA"	326
#16	targeted near/2 (intervention* or treatment or strateg* or administration)	3688

#17 #9 or #10 or #11 or #12 or #13 or #14 or #15 or #16 23725

#18 diagnostic techniques and procedures 2734

#19 MeSH descriptor: [Diagnostic Tests, Routine] explode all trees 240

#20 ((screening or screened or diagnosed or diagnostics or test*)):ti,ab,kw 462451

#21 MeSH descriptor: [Point-of-Care Testing] explode all trees 74

#22 MeSH descriptor: [Clinical Laboratory Techniques] explode all trees 43786

#23 "rapid diagnostic test*" or RDT* 601

#24 ("parasitological diagnosis"):ti,ab,kw 26

#25 ("Parasitologic test*" or "symptom screening"):ti,ab,kw 67

#26 "case detection" or PACD or ACD 918

#27 #18 or #19 or #20 or #21 or #22 or #23 or #24 or #25 or #26 488586

#28 #8 and #17 and #27 682

#29 MeSH descriptor: [Forests] explode all trees 13

#30 MeSH descriptor: [Miners] explode all trees 1

#31 MeSH descriptor: [Military Personnel] explode all trees 955

#32 "Forest-goers" or Vulnerable or Worksites or Farm* or plantation* or mining or miner* or laborers or cultivators or military or "armed forces" or "peace-keepers" or agricultural 43740

#33 ("high risk population*"):ti,ab,kw 4234

#34 MeSH descriptor: [Risk Factors] explode all trees 24812

#35 ("special populations".):ti,ab,kw 138

#36 "high exposure" or "highly exposed" or "high transmission" or hotspot* 692

#37 #29 or #30 or #31 or #32 or #33 or #34 or #35 or #36 72239

#38 #28 and #37 106

#39 "test and treat" 201

#40 "testing and treating" 17

#41 TTaT 3

#42 #39 or #40 or #41 219

#43 #42 and #8 18

#44 #43 or #38 116

Clinicaltrials.gov, WHO ICTRP, ISRCTN registry: malaria and targeted, malaria and test and treat

Appendix 2. Methodology

Figure A. Process Flow Diagram for Review Methodology

Flow diagram demonstrates process for including studies based on review question PICO criteria for synthesis and meta-analysis in parallel to systematic inclusion of contextual evidence that will be integrated with results to support the guideline development panel in formulating final strategy recommendations.

Figure B. Adapted PRISMA Flow Diagram for Study Synthesis

Source: Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, The PRISMA Group (2009). Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. *PLoS Med* 6(7): e1000097. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed1000097

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Study Design	Experimental	Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs, parallel and cluster designs) Randomized cross-over trials Stepped wedge cluster randomized trials Controlled and uncontrolled before and after studies Interrupted time series studies (ITS)
	Observational	Prospective Cohort Case-Control Cross-Sectional Qualitative (focus groups, surveys)
Setting	Country	Region District Village
	Environment	Urban or Rural
	Transmission	Season Endemicity Intensity
	Population Size	
	Study Population	Sample size
Demographics	Participant Characteristics	Age range Gender Other
Methodology	Diagnosis	Clinical or Laboratory-based test
	Diagnostic tool	RDT or Blood smear or other
Treatment	Drug	
	Dosage	
Time period	Study period	Baseline length Intervention length Post intervention length
Infectious Agent	Parasite species	
Baseline	Pre-Intervention measures	Incidence Prevalence
	Background Interventions/ Standard of Care	Vector control ITNs Surveillance Other
	Coverage of background interventions	
Intervention	Intervention population coverage	Target Actual
	Intervention Arms	
	Control Arms	
Outcomes	Epidemiological measures by sex	Incidence of infection Prevalence of infection Elimination Incidence of clinical malaria Number of indigenous cases Drug Resistance Adverse events
Contextual Factors	Acceptability Health equity, equality, and non-discrimination	

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

	Financial and economic considerations
	Feasibility and health system considerations
Other	Contextual study information
	Potential Study biases

Appendix 3. PRISMA Diagram

*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers).

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. BMJ

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

List of Excluded Studies and Reason for Exclusion		
Short Title	Title	Reason excluded
Baiden (2013)	Restricting artemisinin-based combination therapy to test positive malaria in a high-transmission setting in Ghana-a cluster-randomised trial	Cross-referenced or linked article; Not Retrieved - conference proceeding/abstract only
Baiden (2013)	Effects of restricting artemisinin-based combination therapy to test positive malaria in a high-transmission setting in ghana: A cluster randomized trial	Cross-referenced or linked article; Not Retrieved - conference proceeding/abstract only
Bousema (2013)	The impact of hotspot-targeted interventions on malaria transmission: study protocol for a cluster-randomized controlled trial	Population - geographic hotspots not targeted to high risk populations; Protocol
Brooker (2010)	Improving educational achievement and anaemia of school children: design of a cluster randomised trial of school-based malaria prevention and enhanced literacy instruction in Kenya	Protocol -linked to Halliday 2014
Hast (2018)	The use of GPS data loggers to describe spatiotemporal movement patterns and the implications for malaria control in three epidemiologic settings in Southern Africa	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Kachur (2016)	'Beyond "test and treat" - malaria diagnosis for improved pediatric fever management in sub-Saharan Africa' by Emily White Johansson	Study Focus Area - commentary on policy
Krisher (2016)	Successful malaria elimination in the Ecuador-Peru border region: epidemiology and lessons learned	Study Focus Area/Study Design - case study on an elimination program approach not specifically TTaT

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Kunkel (2021)	Choosing interventions to eliminate forest malaria: preliminary results of two operational research studies inside Cambodian forests	Intervention -passive case and reactive case detection in intervention 'arm'; comparator was observational baseline study in same/comparable population.
Lausatianragit (2018)	Coordinated Thailand ministry of public health and royal Thai army-us army civilian-military response to a malaria outbreak in Northeast Thailand	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Lon (2015)	Defining effective, appropriate, implementable strategies for malaria elimination in military forces in Cambodia as a model for mobile populations	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Lover (2018)	A community-randomized trial assessing the effectiveness of targeted active malaria case detection among high-risk populations in southern Lao PDR: Study design and baseline survey results	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Lover (2019)	Study protocol for a cluster-randomized split-plot design trial to assess the effectiveness of targeted active malaria case detection among high-risk populations in Southern Lao PDR (the AcME-Lao study)	Protocol * if study results are available - study can be included for both TTaT and MTaT
Nct (2018)	P. Falciparum Infection Dynamics and Transmission to Inform Elimination (INDIE-1a)	not retrieved - trial registration / intervention & comparison - 2nd study arm weekly active case detection for CCM
Ndyomugyenyi (2012)	Introducing rapid diagnostic tests into community-based management of malaria: Evidence from a cluster-randomized trial in two areas of high and low transmission in Uganda	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Nguon (2018)	Accessing hard-to-reach populations: Forest interventions increase case detection in Pursat province, Cambodia	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only / Study design - uncontrolled cross-sectional survey, doesn't seem to be an intervention study
Rossi (2018)	Closing in on the Reservoir: Proactive Case Detection in High-Risk Groups as a Strategy to Detect Plasmodium falciparum Asymptomatic Carriers in Cambodia	Intervention - TTaT was combined with RCD / Linked to Taffon Pierluigi (2018) which is included for contextual factors
Wang (2019)	Application of community-based and integrated strategy to reduce malaria disease burden in southern Tanzania: the study protocol of China-UK-Tanzania pilot project on malaria control	Protocol; Study focus area - programmatic evaluation of policy
Tsarafihavy (2018)	From Presumed to Confirmation Diagnosis: Improving Testing and Treatment of Malaria in Children under five in Rural Communities in Madagascar	Not retrieved - conference abstract
Ahmed (2019)	Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment and intermittent screening and treatment versus single screening and treatment with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for the control of malaria in pregnancy in Indonesia: a cluster-randomised, open-label, superiority trial	Population - Pregnant women; Comparison - compared to a policy recommendation for IPTp as the 'standard of care'
Dounine (2018)	Malakit: an innovative pilot project to self-diagnose and self-treat malaria among illegal gold miners in the Guiana Shield	Pilot paper on protocol and intervention description

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Halliday et.al. (2012)	Plasmodium falciparum, anaemia and cognitive and educational performance among school children in an area of moderate malaria transmission: baseline results of a cluster randomized trial on the coast of Kenya	Cross-referenced article - linked to Halliday 2014; Brooker 2010
Hoyer (2012)	Focused Screening and Treatment (FSAT): A PCR-Based Strategy to Detect Malaria Parasite Carriers and Contain Drug Resistant P. falciparum, Pailin, Cambodia	Intervention - geographic high-risk locations with mass testing for id of asymptomatic infections; study design - cross sectional survey
Malaria Consortium (2019)	Countering the spread of drug-resistant malaria in northern Cambodia	Not retrieved-report from malaria consortium/protocol/brief
Poespoprodjo (2018)	Intermittent Screening and Treatment for the control of malaria in the first year of life in Papua, Indonesia: A cluster randomized controlled trial	Not retrieved - clinical trial registration
Sutanto (2021)	Serological Screen and Treat Trial for P. Vivax: a Proof-of-concept Trial in Eastern Indonesia	Not retrieved - clinical trial registration
Sondo et. al (2021)	Boosting the Impact of SMC Through Simultaneous Screening and Treatment of Roommates (SMC-RST)	Not retrieved - clinical trial registration

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Thangadurai (2020)	Forest malaria interventions have made remarkable progress in drastically reducing Plasmodium falciparum malaria in Pursat Province, Cambodia	Not retrieved - conference abstract
Tseroni (2020)	Programme for Malaria among Migrants from Malaria Endemic Countries: The Greek Experience in a Receptive and Vulnerable Area	Intervention - included reactive case detection in epi investigation of positive reports
Adinan (2015)	Factors Associated with Testing and Prompt Use of Recommended Antimalarials following Malaria Diagnosis: A Secondary Analysis of 2011-12 Tanzania HIV and Malaria Indicator Survey Data	Exclude for contextual factors; Study Focus Area - descriptive secondary analysis of surveillance data
Babigumira (2017)	Cost-Effectiveness of Strategies for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Febrile Illness in Children	Exclude for contextual factors; Study Focus Area - textbook review of cost effectiveness; not a study
Bennett (2019)	Targeted Surveillance for Forest-based malaria transmission: Results of a cluster randomized controlled trial in southern Lao PDR	Not-retrieved- abstract/conference proceeding/ cross-referenced article
Canavati (2019)	Risk factor assessment for clinical malaria among forest-goers in a pre-elimination setting in Phu Yen Province, Vietnam	Exclude for contextual factors -Did not include CF informaton - included participant interviews from self reported malaria suspicion and health-seeking to local clinic
Castellani (2016)	Impact of Improving Community-Based Access to Malaria Diagnosis and Treatment on Household Costs	Exclude for contextual factors - based on a CHW intervention not TTaT
Chritz (2017)	Malaria control in migrant laborers working in agricultural farms in Metema region, Ethiopia: Current practices, feasibility and acceptability of new malaria interventions	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Dantzer (2018)	Feasibility and acceptability of a peer navigator led malaria focal test and treat intervention targeting high-risk populations in Southern Lao PDR	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only / cross-referenced study abstract
Dantzer (2019)	Feasibility and acceptability of a peer navigator led malaria focal test and treat intervention targeting high-risk populations in southern Lao PDR	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only/ cross-referenced study abstract
Fançony (2021)	Effectiveness of Nutrition and WASH/malaria educational community-based interventions in reducing anemia in children from Angola	Intervention - test and treat was implemented as the control for effectiveness trial of other interventions
Hustedt (2018)	Expanding the health system into the forest: Analysis and response to the challenge of providing malaria services inside forest areas within the greater mekong sub-region in the context of malaria elimination	Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Lopes (2020)	Malaria Test, Treat and Track policy implementation in Angola: a retrospective study to assess the progress achieved after 4 years of programme implementation	Exclude for contextual factors - assessment of knowledge in HCWs
Nct (2018)	Routine Antenatal Care Versus Screening and Treatment of Malaria in Pregnancy in Rwanda	Not retrieved - trial registration
Nct (2018)	Targeted Active Case Detection Among High Risk Populations in Southern Lao Peoples Democratic Republic	Not retrieved; Exclude for contextual factors
Olapeju (2020)	Malaria prevention and care seeking among gold miners in Guyana	Exclude for contextual factors - knowledge, attitudes and practices survey

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Pulford (2016)	Health Worker Compliance with a 'Test And Treat' Malaria Case Management Protocol in Papua New Guinea	Exclude for contextual factors - fever case management evaluation study
Saad (2018)	Pro-active case detection in an area of artemisinin resistance: Identifying asymptomatic carriers and accelerating elimination efforts	Not retrieved - conference abstract; Exclude for contextual factors; Cross-referenced article -linked to Rossi(2018) and Pierluigi (2018)
Staff (2017)	Correction: Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Test-Based versus Presumptive Treatment of Uncomplicated Malaria in Children under Five Years in an Area of High Transmission in Central Ghana	Cross-referenced to Tawiah(2016) - table correction was published
Wijesinghe (2011)	Exploring provider and community responses to the new malaria diagnostic and treatment regime in Solomon Islands	Exclude for contextual factors - study focused on acceptability and perceptions of malaria RDTs and ACTs not the intervention/approach of TTaT
Zurovac (2014)	Major improvements in the quality of malaria case-management under the "test and treat" policy in Kenya	Exclude for contextual factors - study focuses on fever case management in health facilities
Eckhoff (2011)	Modeling for malaria elimination in a variety of transmission settings	Exclude for modeling; Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Gerardin (2017)	Preventing reestablishment of malaria in recently eliminated areas: A modeling study of reactive case detection and adaptive response	Exclude for modeling; Not retrieved - conference proceedings/abstract only
Getachew (2016)	Assessing movement patterns and malaria-associated factors among agricultural migrant workers and the feasibility of implementing new targeted anti-malaria interventions in Amhara region, Ethiopia	Exclude for contextual factors; focused on preferred interventions by migrant workers and who referred participants to a health post; not on TTaT

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Hill (2016)	User and Provider Acceptability of Intermittent Screening and Treatment and Intermittent Preventive Treatment with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine to Prevent Malaria in Pregnancy in Western Kenya	Exclude for contextual factors; population includes pregnant women and IPTp
Hill (2018)	Evaluation of the national policy of single screening and treatment for the prevention of malaria in pregnancy in two districts in Eastern Indonesia: health provider perceptions	Exclude for contextual factors; population includes pregnant women and IPTp
Hoyt (2018)	Intermittent screening and treatment or intermittent preventive treatment compared to current policy of single screening and treatment for the prevention of malaria in pregnancy in Eastern Indonesia: acceptability among health providers and pregnant women	Exclude for contextual factors; population includes pregnant women and IPTp

Appendix 4. Study Characteristics and Assessments

Study. 1 Halliday et. al. (2014)

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	01/2010 - 03/2012
Location	Kenya: Kwale - Mkongani and Shimba Hills; Msambweni - Lunga and Mwereni
Peak transmission season	Perennial; following rainy seasons which are April - July; September - November
Baseline transmission intensity	Moderate, baseline estimates 9-24% prevalence; baseline survey of study population 13%
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>A. funestus</i> , <i>A. gambiae s.l.</i>
Study design	Factorial Cluster-randomized controlled trial
Statistical power calculation	The sample size required for a power of 80% at a two-sided significance level of 5%, was a total of 27 schools in each arm with 50 children per school to detect a 25% reduction in the prevalence of anaemia, which was the primary outcome
Clusters	<p><u>Unit of randomization</u>: School</p> <p><u>Number of clusters selected</u>: 101</p> <p><u>Number of clusters analyzed</u>: 101</p> <p><u>Average cluster size</u>: Baseline: Control - n= 50 clusters; mean (SD) = 47.5 (6.9), range 16-55; Intervention - n = 51; mean (SD) 47.1 (6.1), range 26-60; Follow-up 12 months - Control mean = 43 (6.6) [15-53]; Intervention mean 45.1 (4.4) [34-55]; Follow-up 24 months Control mean 40.5 (6.3) [15,49]; Intervention mean 42.6 (4.9) [33,55]</p>
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<p><u>Total</u>: 13527</p> <p><u>Intervention</u>: 3850 randomized for malaria intervention</p> <p><u>Comparison</u>: 3487 randomized for participation in malaria control arm</p>
Participant characteristics	School-aged children, 5 to 20 years
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	School based intermittent screening and treatment
Comparator	No intervention
Background interventions	Lymphatic filariasis treatment with albendazole and praziquantel Literary and educational assessments Bed nets, high coverage though not specified
Diagnostics	Microscopy: Thick and thin blood films were stained with Giemsa, asexual parasites were counted against 200 white blood cells (WBCs); read independently and blinded by two experts RDT: ParaCheck-Pf device, Orchid Biomedical Systems

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

Drug and manufacturer	artemether-lumefantrine (AL); Coartem, Novartis
Dosage	6 doses over 3 days in four categories (15 kg, 15–24.9 kg, 25–34.9 kg, and 35 kg). AL was given at a dose of 20/120 mg to children ,15 kg, 40/240 mg to children 15–24.9 kg, 60/360 mg to children 25–34.9 kg, and 80/480 mg to those who weighed >35 kg.
Number of rounds per season or year	Five rounds of screening and treatment - March 2010, July 2010, September 2010, March 2011, October 2011; Follow up surveys in March 2011 and March 2012.
TTaT interval	Accordance with school terms; 3-6 months
Duration of the intervention	2 years
TTaT adherence	During the 24 months of intervention, an average of 2,340 children (88.4% of eligible study children) in the 51 intervention schools were screened at each visit. There was an apparent decline in full supervision (a proxy for compliance) with time, falling from 96.9% at the first round to 81.7% at the fifth round.
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement:</u> At 12-months follow-up, 2,148 children in the control schools and 2,298 in the intervention schools provided a finger-prick blood sample for Hb assessment, and at 24 months 2,027 and 2,174 children provided finger-prick samples in the control and intervention groups, respectively. <u>Timepoints:</u> 12 -, and 24-months follow-up <u>Sample size:</u> 12-months: 2298 (intervention), 2148 (control); 24-months: 2174 (intervention); 2027(control)
Adverse Events	<u>Measurement:</u> active surveillance for 48 hours and passive surveillance up to 28 days <u>Timepoints:</u> up to 28 days <u>Sample size:</u> 2030 intervention arm, control arm not reported
Severe Adverse Events	<u>Measurement:</u> death <u>Timepoint:</u> 24 months <u>Sample size:</u> 12-months: 2298 (intervention), 2148 (control); 24-months: 2174 (intervention); 2027(control)

Study 1. Halliday et. al. (2014)

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection in the group targeted by the intervention</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	"Schools were randomised to one of four groups, receiving either: (i) IST alone; (ii) the literacy intervention alone; (iii) both interventions combined; or (iv) control group where neither intervention was implemented...,The 101 schools were randomised in

		<p>two stages with each stage conducted during a public ceremony. Schools are aggregated into sets of between three and six closely located schools, which regularly meet and share information, supported by a Ministry of Education Teacher Advisory Centre tutor. The IST intervention was randomly allocated at the level of the school, with the 101 schools re-stratified by (i) literacy intervention group assignment and (ii) quintiles of average school exam scores.)”</p> <p>The geographical heterogeneity observed in the prevalence of <i>P. falciparum</i> infection is likely to reflect a complexity of factors that influence vector distribution and density as well as vector–human contact and human infection.</p>
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	No randomization occurred at the school level and students were given the assigned intervention of their school.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	<p>The study was not blinded.</p> <p>No indication of deviation from intended intervention 1. it was not possible to blind the parents, participants, or field officers delivering the IST intervention to experimental assignment, which could have led to a possible “John Henry” effect whereby children in the control group adjust their behavior as they know they are not receiving the intervention, for example in risk aversion and treatment seeking behavior. 2) Second, study children’s access to alternative malaria treatments outside of the school-based IST rounds was not monitored during the two years of the trial. 3) the lack of multiple testing adjustments may have increased the possibility of type 1 error, and results should be interpreted in light of this possible error, but it is unlikely to have masked a beneficial effect of IST.</p>
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Of the 5,233 children enrolled initially, 4,446 (85.0%) were included in the 12-month follow-up health survey and 4,201 (80.3%) were included in the 24-month health survey. At 12 and 24 months, children lost to follow-up across both study arms were largely similar to children followed up.
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	<p>Lowest cluster range was 26 at any timepoint (figure 3)</p> <p>The analyses described here correspond to a pre-specified statistical analysis plan, approved by both</p>

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

		the data monitoring committee and trial steering committee before any data were examined.
		Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	The primary pre-specified analysis adjusted for age (as a continuous variable), sex, and the baseline measure of the outcome, except for baseline <i>P. falciparum</i> , which was not measured in the control schools.
Risk of bias		
Outcome: Adverse Events		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	<p>"Schools were randomised to one of four groups, receiving either: (i) IST alone; (ii) the literacy intervention alone; (iii) both interventions combined; or (iv) control group where neither intervention was implemented...,The 101 schools were randomised in two stages with each stage conducted during a public ceremony. Schools are aggregated into sets of between three and six closely located schools, which regularly meet and share information, supported by a Ministry of Education Teacher Advisory Centre tutor. The IST intervention was randomly allocated at the level of the school, with the 101 schools re-stratified by (i) literacy intervention group assignment and (ii) quintiles of average school exam scores.)"</p> <p>The geographical heterogeneity observed in the prevalence of <i>P. falciparum</i> infection is likely to reflect a complexity of factors that influence vector distribution and density as well as vector–human contact and human infection.</p>
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	No randomization occurred at the school level and students were given the assigned intervention of their school.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	The study was not blinded. No indication of deviation from intended intervention
D3: Missing outcome data	Some Concerns	Adverse events were monitored by the study team for 24 hours after each treatment, and a further 28 days thereafter using a passive surveillance system in schools. Adverse events not monitored in control arm

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Adverse events were monitored using passive surveillance in the schools for up to 24 months follow-up period.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Adverse events were monitored by the study team for 24 hours after each treatment, and a further 28 days thereafter using a passive surveillance system in schools. Travel costs were reimbursed, and treatment charges waived. Adverse experiences were monitored until the event was cured or had stabilised. Agranulocytosis and hepatotoxicity not monitored.
Risk of bias		
Outcome: Severe Adverse Events		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	<p>“Schools were randomised to one of four groups, receiving either: (i) IST alone; (ii) the literacy intervention alone; (iii) both interventions combined; or (iv) control group where neither intervention was implemented...The 101 schools were randomised in two stages with each stage conducted during a public ceremony. Schools are aggregated into sets of between three and six closely located schools, which regularly meet and share information, supported by a Ministry of Education Teacher Advisory Centre tutor. The IST intervention was randomly allocated at the level of the school, with the 101 schools re-stratified by (i) literacy intervention group assignment and (ii) quintiles of average school exam scores.)”</p> <p>The geographical heterogeneity observed in the prevalence of <i>P. falciparum</i> infection is likely to reflect a complexity of factors that influence vector distribution and density as well as vector–human contact and human infection.</p>
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	No randomization occurred at the school level and students were given the assigned intervention of their school.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	The study was not blinded. No indication of deviation from intended intervention
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	During the 24 months of follow-up, 11 children died: five in the intervention group and six in the control group. Cause of death was investigated and included yellow fever, heart defect, leukemia, drowning, trauma, pneumonia, and pediatric HIV.

Targeted Test and Treat in High-Risk Populations

D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Mortality was monitored for study participants during the 24-month follow-up period.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Study 2. Baiden et. al. (2016)

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	02/2009-07/2012
Location	Ghana: the forest-savannah transition zone
Peak transmission season	Perennial
Baseline transmission intensity	High: (EIR) estimated at 231–269 infective bites per person per year
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles funestus</i> and <i>Anopheles gambiae</i>
Study design	Factorial Cluster-randomized controlled trial
Statistical power calculation	To reach 80% power at 95% significance and detect a 20% difference in the incidence of malaria between the two comparison groups at least 30 clusters (15 per arm) and 200 person-years at risk (PYAR) per cluster. This was based on the following expectations: (1) Incidence of malaria in the CJ arm would be 0.8 episode/ 1 per child per year (the rate observed in a group of < 24-month-old children in Navrongo, Ghana)
Clusters	<u>Unit of randomization</u> : Health center; Thirty-two health centers were stratified by districts, ranked by the number of Diphtheria-Pertussis-Tetanus1 (DPT1) vaccinations given in the facility in the preceding year and paired according to the rank within each district <u>Number of clusters selected</u> : 32 <u>Number of clusters analyzed</u> : 32 <u>Average cluster size</u> : 95 participants
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 3046 <u>Intervention</u> : 1585 in the RDT arm <u>Comparison</u> : 1579 clinical judgement arm
Participant characteristics	Children < 24 months
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	RDT-based testing w/fever screening and treatment
Comparator	Standard of care/ clinical judgement
Background interventions	Bed nets: 74.4% in intervention; 79% in CJ group All providers given refresher training in IMCI management of febrile illnesses every 4-6months

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	Febrile illness and morbidity questionnaires by field investigators
Diagnostics	Two brands of mRDTs procured through the Ghana National Malaria Control Programme, CareStart™ and First Response™ Microscopy: blood smears read independently by two expert microscopists at the reference laboratory at the Kintampo Health Research Centre (KHRC)
Drug and manufacturer	Nationally-approved first line ACTs: artesunate-amodiaquine, artemether-lumefantrine and dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine
Dosage	Not specified
Number of rounds per season or year	One round for children who reported with fever; time to first episode of febrile illness
TTaT interval	n/a
Duration of the intervention	2 years
TTaT adherence	As a deviation from the study protocol, 8 out of 5799 (0.14%) cases that presented to CJ-arm facilities had RDT performed.
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Incidence of malaria infection (community level)	<u>Measurement</u> : survival time to malaria after the first episode of a febrile illness and person-time to first episode of febrile illness <u>Timepoints</u> : 24-months follow-up <u>Sample size</u> : 1527 in the RDT arm and 1519 in the CJ- arm
Severe Adverse Events	<u>Measurement</u> : death <u>Timepoint</u> : 24 months <u>Sample size</u> : Control = 1498 RDT arm = 1512

Study 2. Baiden et. al. (2016)

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Incidence of malaria infection</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	“Thirty-two health centers were stratified by districts, ranked by the number of Diphtheria-Pertussis-Tetanus1 (DPT1) vaccinations given in the facility in the preceding year and paired according to the rank within each district. Within each pair of health facilities, one was allocated randomly to implement test-based (RDT-arm) management of malaria, while the other health facility within the pair was allocated to implement the clinical judgement (CJ arm) approach.”

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		No significant differences in the characteristics and comparability of children enrolled into the two arms of the study.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	<p>Investigators enumerated all households that were located within 2km radius of the selected health centers and enrolled one hundred children per health facility who met the inclusion criteria; they enrolled children living closest to the selected health centers and extended outwards circumferentially until the target of 100 children was achieved.</p> <p>No significant differences in the characteristics and comparability of children enrolled into the two arms of the study.</p>
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	<p>Caregivers had to provide consent to participation and received assistance for enrollment in the national insurance scheme as well home visits from field workers.</p> <p>All children received clinical assessment for malaria appropriately that was not obviously linked to the intervention assignment from a service delivery standpoint. Children in the RDT group were tested using RDTs from the NMCP and were also treated for any concurrent illnesses according to IMCI guidelines. In the control group children who presented with fever were not tested for malaria. The treatment for malaria in these facilities was presumptive and based on presenting clinical symptoms and signs. The treatment of all other ailments were based on the IMCI guidelines.</p> <p>The fieldworkers stationed in each (intervention and control) health facility helped to ensure compliance with the protocol by reminding attending clinicians about the protocol of the study, as applicable to the particular health centre. This was reinforced during the 4–6 monthly training sessions that were held for health workers in both intervention and control facilities.</p> <p>A multilevel Poisson model assuming unstructured covariance was used to estimate the incidence of malaria over the 24-month period to account for</p>

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		repeat episodes of malaria within a child, and clustering by health facility.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	In control and intervention group 405 and 355 individuals were not seen at least every 100 days post follow-up initiation. Per protocol analysis produced similar results as the ITT analysis
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Data were double-entered using FoxPro version 9. The analysis was conducted using STATA version 12.
D5: Selection of the reported result	High risk	A Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) periodically reviewed safety parameters and incidence of malaria and anaemia. The DSMB also approved the final analysis plan. Conducted a multi-level Poisson to calculate incidence and rate ratios for comparison in study arms, but did not perform a generalized model accounting for potential demographics and confounders to assess risk of malaria infection in study arms.

Risk of bias

Outcome: Serious Adverse Events

Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	“Thirty-two health centers were stratified by districts, ranked by the number of Diphtheria-Pertussis-Tetanus1 (DPT1) vaccinations given in the facility in the preceding year and paired according to the rank within each district. Within each pair of health facilities, one was allocated randomly to implement test-based (RDT-arm) management of malaria, while the other health facility within the pair was allocated to implement the clinical judgement (CJ arm) approach.” No significant differences in the characteristics and comparability of children enrolled into the two arms of the study.
D1b: Timing of identification or	Low risk	Investigators enumerated all households that were located within 2km radius of the selected health

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recruitment of participants	<p>centers and enrolled one hundred children per health facility who met the inclusion criteria; they enrolled children living closest to the selected health centers and extended outwards circumferentially until the target of 100 children was achieved.</p> <p>No significant differences in the characteristics and comparability of children enrolled into the two arms of the study.</p>	
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	<p>Low risk</p>	<p>Caregivers had to provide consent to participation and received assistance for enrollment in the national insurance scheme as well home visits from field workers.</p> <p>All children received clinical assessment for malaria appropriately that was not obviously linked to the intervention assignment from a service delivery standpoint. Children in the RDT group were tested using RDTs from the NMCP and were also treated for any concurrent illnesses according to IMCI guidelines. In the control group children who presented with fever were not tested for malaria. The treatment for malaria in these facilities was presumptive and based on presenting clinical symptoms and signs. The treatment of all other ailments were based on the IMCI guidelines.</p> <p>The fieldworkers stationed in each (intervention and control) health facility helped to ensure compliance with the protocol by reminding attending clinicians about the protocol of the study, as applicable to the particular health centre. This was reinforced during the 4–6 monthly training sessions that were held for health workers in both intervention and control facilities.</p> <p>A multilevel Poisson model assuming unstructured covariance was used to estimate the incidence of malaria over the 24-month period to account for repeat episodes of malaria within a child, and clustering by health facility.</p>
D3: Missing outcome data	<p>Low risk</p>	<p>In control and intervention group 405 and 355 individuals were not seen at least every 100 days post</p>

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		follow-up initiation. Deaths were recorded in both the clinical judgement and intervention arms
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Data were double-entered using FoxPro version 9. The analysis was conducted using STATA version 12.
D5: Selection of the reported result	High risk	Although mortality was measured in the study, it was assumed a priori that the number of deaths would not be sufficient to detect any significant difference between the two arms.

Study 3. Cohee et. al. (2021)

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2015
Location	Southern Malawi: Maseya, Makhuwira, Bvumbwe, Ngowe
Peak transmission season	Rainy season (April–May) and Dry season (September–October)
Baseline transmission intensity	Moderate Maseya and Makjuwira: >40% parasite prevalence in school children Bvumbwe and Ngowe : lower, seasonally varied transmission (> two-fold seasonal prevalence difference)
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	Not specified
Study design	Cohort Study
Statistical power calculation	n/a
Cohorts	<u>Unit of randomization:</u> Grade/Classroom in school by village <u>Number of participants by group:</u> Fifteen students per grade-level (grade 1–8) <u>Number of cohorts assessed:</u> 2 cohorts, rainy season and dry season
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total:</u> 960 <u>Before:</u> 786 <u>After:</u> 616
Participant characteristics	School-aged children, 5 to 15 years
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	School based intermittent screening and treatment
Comparator	Pre - intervention baseline of cohort
Background interventions	Bed nets: 47% (reported bed net use the previous night)

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Diagnostics	qRT-PCR: finger prick; filter paper (Whatmann #3) dried blood spots and whole blood in RNA preservative RDT from Standard of Care - histidine rich protein 2 RDT from Paracheck Orchid Biomedical Systems, Goa, India or SD Bioline, Standard Diagnostics Inc., Suwon City, Republic of Korea
Drug and manufacturer	artemether-lumefantrine (AL); Novartis Pharma AG or Ajanta Pharma Ltd.
Dosage	weight-based
Number of rounds per season or year	one round per cohort
TTaT interval	n/a; follow-up at 1, 2 and 6 weeks
Duration of the intervention	6 weeks
TTaT adherence	Not specified
OUTCOMES	
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : At baseline and all follow-up visits, finger-prick blood was obtained for molecular detection of any-stage parasites and gametocytes <u>Timepoints</u> : baseline, 1-, 2-, 6-weeks <u>Sample size</u> : 786 'before'; 616 'after'

Study 3. Cohee et. al. (2021) Outcome: Prevalence of malaria infection in group targeted by the intervention

D1	BIAS DUE TO CONFOUNDING - LOW
	1.1 Key variables that could have a confounding effect were assessed in bivariate and multivariable models between participants at baseline. Potential confounders were then accounted for in final statistical analyses and/or stratified (e.g. seasonality, age)
D2	Bias due to selection of participants - LOW
	2.1 Sites selected from 30 previously studied sites in southern Malawi 2.1 Fifteen students per grade-level (grades 1–8) were sampled using a random number generator. 2.4 Enrolled students were interviewed at baseline (1–2 weeks after enrollment), one-, two-, and six-week visits about bed net use the night prior, current or recent illness, and antimalarial treatment.
D3	Bias in classification of interventions - LOW
	3.1, 3.2 Primary school students in four schools were screened for infection using a rapid diagnostic test (RDT). If positive, students were treated with artemether-lumefantrine. 3.3 Subsequent gametocyte carriage in treated and untreated students was assessed by qRT-PCR after one, two, and six weeks. 3.3 At baseline and all follow-up visits, finger-prick blood was obtained for molecular detection of any-stage parasites (filter paper dried blood spots) and gametocytes (whole blood in RNA preservative). At the final visit, parents were interviewed about their child's health during the

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	study and students' health passports (individual portable medical records) reviewed to identify intercurrent fever or malaria treatment.
D4	Bias due to deviations from intended interventions - LOW 4.1 No evidence of deviations from intended intervention
D5	Bias due to missing data - LOW 5.1 Figure S2 - Enrollment flow chart - 960 randomly selected; 814 for consent; 792 eligible; 786 enrolled; complete follow-up 616 (78%) 5.1 By sampling 320 (10 students/grade/school in each season), we would have 80% power to detect a 40% decrease in the prevalence of infection after the screen-and-treat intervention. 5.2; 5.3; 5.4 Figure S2 - Rainy season cohort 94 excluded for missing visits & subsequent data; Dry season cohort 76 excluded for missing visits & subsequent data 5.5 Final included participants at follow up = 616 (78%); rainy season 311 (77%) and dry season 305 (80%); just under the power sample size estimate of 320
D6	Bias in measurements of outcomes - LOW 6.1 No evidence of influence by knowledge of intervention received on methods and analysis 6.2 -6.4 No evidence of methodological errors on outcome assessments
D7	7.1, 7.2 Contribution to transmission was evaluated four ways: (1) gametocyte prevalence defined as the proportion of participants with any gametocytes; (2) gametocyte density; (3) total gametocyte burden calculated as the sum of participant gametocyte densities; and (4) prevalence of infections with ≥ 10 gametocytes/microliter (μl) 7.3 Only two subgroups used for rainy and dry seasonal cohorts
OVERALL	MODERATE -The study provides sound evidence for a non-randomized study but cannot be considered comparable to a well-performed randomized trial

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